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STRENGTHENING EVIDENCE-BASED DECISION MAKING IN FRAGILE AND CONFLICT-AFFECTED STATES

Insights from Ukraine's National Evaluation System

2025

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Abstract

Since Russia's full-scale invasion, international support for recovery and reconstruction in Ukraine has increased significantly, a development that was paralleled by Ukraine's official candidacy for European Union (EU) accession in June 2022. This discussion paper examines how evidence-based decision making can be strengthened in fragile and conflict-affected states, using Ukraine's national evaluation system, its capacities, the ongoing reconstruction and the EU accession process as a case study. This discussion paper theoretically builds on the findings regarding challenges to evidence-based decision making in international civilian interventions in fragile and conflict-affected states. Methodologically, the discussion paper is based on a qualitative case study analysis and is the product of a collaboration between the German Institute for Development Evaluation (DEval) and members of the Ukrainian Evaluation Association (UEA). It combines international and domestic perspectives on evaluation and evaluation systems.

The discussion paper identifies a fragmented monitoring and evaluation (M&E) landscape in Ukraine and insufficient capacities for evidence-based decision making. Although M&E of public policies is included in different regulations and structures, actual evaluation practices are limited. The absence of a national legal framework, lack of awareness and limited political will among state actors constrain evidence- and learning-oriented policy making. Some non-state actors, such as civil society organisations (CSOs), have demonstrated emerging M&E experience. However, inconsistent professional standards and few educational and training opportunities in the field limit evaluation capacities. Despite ongoing hostilities, Ukraine has demonstrated resilience in maintaining core state functions – but the war has further compounded existing structural weaknesses.

The discussion paper identifies a critical tension: recovery, reconstruction and the EU accession process all require robust M&E systems and an evidence-based approach, but Ukraine's national evaluation practices remain rudimentary. Key findings emphasise that fostering an evaluation culture requires long-term transformation, and effective enhancement of the evaluation practice demands establishing robust institutional frameworks that systematically embed evaluation within public administration structures. Development partners, particularly through EU accession processes and reconstruction funding, can strongly incentivise evidence-informed decision making and the establishment of M&E practices.

These findings have broader implications for international development partners and domestic stakeholders engaged in fragile and conflict-affected states concerning the strengthening of evidence-based decision making in long-term development, recovery and reconstruction, and institutional reform. Building evaluation systems is a complex, multifaceted process that faces political, contextual and conflict-related challenges, so the paper concludes that this process must begin early, be grounded in national ownership, and reflect the political and administrative realities of the specific context. This will require co-ordinated structures to harmonise international assistance with national systems, as well as context-responsive approaches that build on a deep understanding of the evaluation system, capacities and actors.

Keywords: Ukraine, evaluation system, evidence-based decision making, fragility, war, administrative capacities, reform processes, capacity development, EU accession process, recovery and reconstruction, conflict

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AA	Association Agreement
ACLED	Armed Conflict Location and Event Data
ALNAP	Active Learning Network for Accountability and Performance
CMU	Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine
CSO	Civil society organisation
DEval	German Institute for Development Evaluation
DREAM	Digital Restoration Ecosystem for Accountable Management
ECD	Evaluation Capacity Development
EU	European Union
EES	European Evaluation Society
GDP	Gross domestic product
GEI	Global Evaluation Initiative
GIS	Geographic information system
GIZ	German Agency for International Cooperation
IDOS	German Institute of Development and Sustainability
IDP	Internally displaced person
IER	Institute for Economic Research and Policy Consulting
ILO	International Labour Organization
IPA	Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance
INCE	National Evaluation Capacities Index
INESAN	Institute for Evaluations and Social Analyses
IPDET	International Program for Development Evaluation Training
ITA	International Technical Assistance
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
MESA	Monitoring and Evaluation Systems Analysis
NACP	National Agency on Corruption Prevention
NAUCS	National Agency of Ukraine on Civil Service
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
RISE	Reconstruction Integrity, Sustainability and Efficiency
RDNA	Rapid Damage and Needs Assessment
SURGe	Support to Ukraine's Government Reforms
UEA	Ukrainian Evaluation Association
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNHCR	United Nations Refugee Agency
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
VOPE	Voluntary Organisation for Professional Evaluation
VRU	Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine (Parliament)

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Rationale and Relevance

Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine represents a critical turning point, transforming a previously gradual erosion of the multilateral world order into an open and violent confrontation, and intensifying the systemic competition between authoritarian and democratic regimes. This shift coincides with accelerating trends of autocratization, deepening political polarization (Leininger et al., 2024) and significant reductions in state support for international development aid (OECD, 2025a). The spread of disinformation and misinformation, which is now seen as one of the greatest short-term global risks, is increasingly associated with the dynamics of state-based armed conflicts (World Economic Forum, 2024). Empirical evidence suggests not only an increase in the number of armed conflicts worldwide, but also an escalation in their severity in recent years (Rustad, 2025; World Bank Group, 2020). According to the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), a quarter of the world's population now live in contexts characterised by high or extreme fragility (OECD, 2025b). Consequently, the international environment in which the global – particularly Western – community operates has become significantly more complex and volatile, posing new and multifaceted challenges. The ability of states and international actors to promote sustainable development and peace depends crucially on their capacity to make informed, evidence-based decisions

Recovering and reconstructing Ukraine following Russia's full-scale invasion is an immense challenge, not only for the country itself but also for the international community. Russia's invasion has caused profound human suffering, widespread displacement and extensive physical destruction, affecting all aspects of life (World Bank et al., 2025). It is essential to initiate recovery and reconstruction efforts now, despite the ongoing war, to address urgent humanitarian and infrastructural needs and lay the foundation for Ukraine's long-term stability, resilience, development and EU integration (Bjerde, 2023; Grävingsholt et al., 2023). The INFORM Severity Index measures the severity of the crisis following the war at 4.3 out of 5, highlighting the significant impact on the people (EC, 2025a). This crisis has been described as "one of the largest humanitarian crises" (IOM, 2023: 4) and the "largest displacement crisis in Europe since World War II" (UNHCR, 2025a). In January 2025, the United Nations Refugee Agency (UNHCR) reported 6.8 million refugees from Ukraine globally, with 6.3 million hosted in Europe (UNHCR, 2025b). By December 2024, 3.7 million Ukrainian internally displaced persons (IDPs) were registered (IOM, 2025).

At the same time, the war has prompted an unprecedented wave of support for Ukraine from Western allies and other international partners. When Russia began its full-scale invasion into Ukraine, aid increased tremendously (Ministry of National Unity of Ukraine, 2023). According to the Kiel Institute for the World Economy (see Figure 1), since the start of the full-scale invasion, Ukraine has been internationally supported by a running total of more than 293.3 billion euros (April 2025), including financial, humanitarian and military support (Kiel Institute for the World Economy, 2025; Trebesch et al., 2023). As of August 2025, 889 international development assistance projects were registered in Ukraine, of which 785 (88%) had been launched after the full-scale invasion began (SCMU, 2025). The estimated cost of total recovery and reconstruction over the next ten years is 524 billion US dollars, with direct damage to buildings and infrastructure alone accounting for 176 billion US dollars (World Bank et al., 2025). The most affected sectors include housing (over 57 billion US dollars), transport (over 36 billion US dollars), energy and extractives (over 20 billion US dollars), and commerce and industry (over 17 billion US dollars) (World Bank et al., 2025).

In light of these extensive reconstruction needs, the country's recovery will require more than just financial resources – Ukraine needs strategic, evidence-informed policy making to build back better.⁸

Furthermore, Ukraine's process of joining the EU requires the country to reform its legislation to align with EU law. Ukraine is the only EU candidate country to have been granted candidate status during an ongoing war, having applied for EU membership one week after the start of Russia's full-scale invasion. It became an EU candidate country on 23 June 2022 and opened accession negotiations in November 2023. The European Council adopted a negotiating framework in June 2024 (EC, 2024a).

Figure 1 Newly Allocated Support to Ukraine since the Start of Russia's Full-Scale Invasion: Cumulative Flows (February 2022 - April 2025)

Source: DEval, own illustration based on the Ukraine Support Tracker (Kiel Institute for the World Economy, 2025; Trebesch et al., 2023). Financing attributed to "Europe" includes geographic Europe (bilateral support) and EU funding (European Commission and Council).

Against the backdrop of significant recovery and reconstruction needs caused by the ongoing war and the EU acquis reform requirements, this paper asks how evidence-based decision making can be strengthened in fragile and conflict-affected states such as Ukraine. To address this question, the discussion paper uses a mapping approach, considering the National Evaluation Capacities Index (INCE) and the Monitoring and Evaluation Systems Analysis (MESA) analytical and diagnostic tools to analyse the Ukrainian evaluation system and its structures, actors, and capacities in the context of the war. In doing so, the paper addresses a theoretical and methodological gap: research on evidence-based decision making in fragile and conflict-affected states, specifically from a national perspective, remains scarce (Better Evaluation Knowledge, 2025; GEI, 2022).

⁸ The principle of "building back better" involves using of "post-disaster recovery, rehabilitation and reconstruction phases to increase the level of resilience by integrating disaster risk reduction measures in the restoration of infrastructure and societal systems, as well as in the revitalization of livelihoods systems, economies and the environment" (Oriol et al., 2024). In the case of Ukraine, the build back better approach needs to be applied to reconstruction planning during the recovery and reconstruction phases. This includes improved energy efficiency, universal access, critical modernization measures, disaster and climate resilience, and decarbonization, as well as green, resilient, inclusive and sustainable recovery standards (World Bank et al., 2024). This will lay the foundations for a stronger, more sustainable future within the EU (EC, 2025b).

To address these issues, the paper takes a dual approach. Firstly, the role of national evaluation systems in contexts shaped by conflict or fragility is examined. Secondly, the national focus is linked to the international perspective, to examine the challenges associated with evidence-based decision making in international efforts such as joint recovery and reconstruction initiatives. This combination of perspectives is also reflected in the collaboration between international and Ukrainian domestic evaluators – members of the UEA and DEval – enabling different viewpoints to be considered. Empirically, the paper examines the current state of Ukraine's national evaluation system by describing its institutional structures, enabling conditions and key actors (sub-question 1). It further explores how armed conflict, and its related challenges shape the development and institutionalization of national evaluation practices, as well as the use of evidence in public decision making (sub-question 2). Furthermore, the paper considers the role of external drivers, such as reconstruction and recovery efforts and the EU enlargement process, in fostering and strengthening national evaluation systems and capacities (sub-question 3).

These questions are based on the rationale that the multiple needs stemming from the war – human, social, political and environmental – require urgent action, as well as strategic, sustainable recovery and reconstruction. The paper builds on the assumption that effective M&E supports the evidence-based prioritization and sequencing of policy actions. Moreover, it contributes to addressing the challenge that the scale of needs frequently surpasses administrative absorption capacity in these contexts (Institute for State Effectiveness, n.d.). Policy making in fragile and conflict-affected states is particularly demanding, as both conditions share structural barriers which hinder sustainable development and constrain the effective fulfilment of state functions. Crises – of which armed conflict is one form, such as the war against Ukraine – are often highly complex and dynamic, making it difficult to address their full scope or anticipate long-term consequences. This volatility makes it more complex to formulate policies, particularly if core state functions are already weak or constrained (BMI, 2014; EC, n.d.; Klein and Schubert, 2011). In fragile and conflict-affected states, national institutions often experience severe disruptions due to accumulated risks, existing vulnerabilities and weakened resilience, which in turn hamper governance and the reliable delivery of public services (OECD, 2025b; World Bank Group, 2020, 2024). For the Ukrainian government, access to reliable data and robust analytical capacity is essential to navigate international assistance and respond to highly complex challenges. In particular, strategic evaluations are a key tool for integrating evidence into the policy cycle (Faust et al., 2023; OECD, 2005). By assessing the effectiveness of public interventions, evaluations enhance accountability, support learning and enable more informed decision making. They also facilitate adaptive policy design by helping to identify what works, for whom and under what conditions.

Strengthening evaluation capacity also aligns with international principles, notably the 2005 Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness, which calls for harmonization, the use of country systems and a focus on results-based management, including strong M&E procedures and structures (OECD, 2005). However, implementing these commitments is still a challenge. In practice, individual development partners tend to rely on their own M&E systems, which places an additional burden on partner governments with limited capacity. Furthermore, evaluation results and lessons learnt are often not fully disseminated, particularly within highly politicised environments (GPEDC, 2025). These challenges are further exacerbated by armed conflict, fragility – including limited state capacity – and the spread of disinformation and misinformation, as is currently and increasingly the case in Ukraine. Considering the complexities for both national policy makers and international development partners, this paper argues for a greater emphasis on evidence-based decision making from the outset, particularly by developing and integrating national evaluation systems in reform processes. Given Ukraine's substantial financial support for reconstruction and the EU accession process, it is important to prioritise evidence-based approaches today so that these are continued following the war's conclusion. Strengthening the evidence-based policy-making system, as part of ongoing externally driven processes, will better equip development partners and national actors with strategies and options for a post-war environment. As Aghumian (2022) notes:

“Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) may seem a superfluous worry in times of fragility and conflict. The complexity and urgency of issues that countries with such challenges face are overwhelming. [...] However, strong M&E systems can have an even deeper impact on countries that are marred by fragility, conflict, and violence.”

The case of Ukraine illustrates the following tension: although M&E has become more difficult to promote and implement in the conditions of ongoing war and crisis (as well as alongside parallel recovery and reconstruction efforts), the need for it is even more acute and pressing. This paper identifies entry points for strengthening Ukraine's national evaluation system and capacities to contribute to more transparent, accountable, and effective recovery and reconstruction efforts both nationally and internationally – while also supporting the country's path to EU accession, as postulated in the Lugano Principles agreed in July 2022 (Ukraine Recovery Conference, 2022). Ukraine's position within the Eastern Partnership and its EU candidate status provide a unique window of opportunity for external support to advance national evaluation system reforms and capacities. The experiences of previous EU enlargement countries, such as Romania and Poland, demonstrate that the EU accession process can serve as a powerful driver for institutional transformation. In these contexts, conditionality led to improvements in public administration, the development of national evaluation infrastructure and the integration of evidence-based decision making (Stockmann et al., 2020).

For Ukraine, these processes are a timely and important opportunity, but also a requirement, for the institutionalization and professionalisation of M&E practices. The recovery and reconstruction process and the EU accession track both act as external leverages that can help institutionalise M&E and embed evidence-based governance practices in the long term. However, the case study's empirical evidence suggests that strong M&E capacities need to be implemented within the national administration early on. Currently, there is no proper national M&E system in place in Ukraine. Regulations in this regard are fragmented, and there is no significant culture of evaluation among government institutions.

1.2 Methodological Approach

This section outlines the discussion paper's methodological approach and reflects on its limitations. In light of the outlined opportunities and challenges of increased evidence orientation, this paper explores how evidence-based decision making can be strengthened in fragile and conflict-affected states such as Ukraine. To address the main question, the following three sub-questions guide the discussion:

1. What is the current state of Ukraine's evaluation system, including its institutional structures, enabling conditions and key actors?
2. How do armed conflict and its related challenges affect the development and institutionalization of national evaluation systems, as well as the use of evidence in public decision making?
3. To what extent and in what ways do external drivers, such as reconstruction and recovery efforts and the EU enlargement process, contribute to establishing national evaluation systems and capacities?

To respond to these research questions, the discussion paper uses an innovative mapping methodology to analyse evaluation structures and capacities in a national context heavily influenced by large-scale financial aid and war. The discussion paper considers two diagnostic tools: INCE and MESA (see Box 1).⁹ These tools were used as models to describe and diagnose the main features of the national evaluation system in Ukraine. The empirical work on the national evaluation system focused on structures, practices and

⁹ The case study is built on the analytical frameworks of INCE and MESA and focuses on selected questions of these tools. These models were adapted to the Ukrainian context, with additional attention given to M&E tools related to war damages, reconstruction and recovery and Ukraine's EU accession as potential driving forces for developing the M&E system in the country. This is considered the first such comprehensive undertaking of mapping the evaluation system in Ukraine; however, a baseline study on the Ukrainian evaluation capacities conducted by the UEA in 2012 was taken into account for this analysis (Stolyarenko et al., 2012).

capacities related to evaluation, while also considering monitoring as a related field.¹⁰ As a first step, the authors conducted a theoretical analysis and reviewed relevant documents on evaluation systems, conflict, fragility and EU integration. This included a practice-oriented analysis of lessons learnt from previous international civilian engagements in fragile and conflict-affected states.

Methodologically, the paper presents a qualitative case study analysis of Ukraine's national evaluation system and institutional capacities. The mapping exercise on the case study was conducted by a team of members of the UEA – Dr Olha Krasovska, Dr Vitalii Gryga, Ms Liubov Margolina, Ms Vira Nedzvedska and Ms Iryna Lupashko – supported by DEval. The empirical data was collected during October and November 2024, both online and on site. The mapping exercise is complemented by a literature analysis and document reviews; the former is situated in the broader contexts of evaluation in fragile and conflict-affected states, as well as within the EU enlargement process. These two dimensions are applicable to the Ukrainian context but allow for transferable lessons to similar settings. Ukraine was selected as the case study for this paper due to its high level of international political relevance and because of the substantial support provided by international partners for its recovery and reconstruction efforts. This discussion paper is the product of an ongoing co-operation between DEval and members of the UEA.

The qualitative case study analysis is based on a combination of different methods and data sources, using both primary and secondary data. In detail, the following methods and data sources were used:

4. Analysis of data and indices on the political and socio-economic situation; reports and data on the war, recovery and reconstruction, and EU integration; reports by international development partners; and review of academic literature
5. A comprehensive analysis of primary and secondary documents on the case study, including on the Ukrainian legislation, open access data and dashboards, and reports
6. Semi-structured interviews with representatives from the Secretariat of the Cabinet of Ministries of Ukraine; line ministries, including the Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine, Ministry of Social Policy of Ukraine and Ministry of Finance of Ukraine; and the Parliament, specifically the Parliamentary Faction Secretariat
7. A group discussion with representatives of Ukrainian delegates participating in the Eastern Partnership Civil Society Forum Civil Society Summit 2024, held in November 2024
8. An online survey with Ukrainian CSOs¹¹ (n=50)¹²
9. A validation workshop, with 18 UEA members participating to triangulate findings

10 The discussion paper follows the definition of M&E adopted by the OECD Development Assistance Committee (DAC) (OECD, 2023): monitoring is “a continuing process that involves the systematic collection or collation of data (on specified indicators or other types of information). Provides the management and other stakeholders of an intervention with indications of the extent of implementation progress, achievement of intended results, occurrence of unintended results, use of allocated funds and other important intervention and context-related information.” (OECD, 2023: 44) Evaluation is “[t]he systematic and objective assessment of a planned, ongoing or completed intervention, its design, implementation and results. [...] Evaluation also refers to the process of determining the worth or significance of an intervention. An evaluation should provide information that is credible and useful, enabling the incorporation of lessons learned into decision-making processes” (OECD, 2023: 31).

11 In this study, CSOs are understood as a broader range of non-state, not-for-profit entities formed by citizens to address issues in the public interest, including both formally registered and not-registered community groups, faith-based organisations, professional associations, trade unions and other voluntary associations that contribute to civil society (NGO Report, 2023).

12 The CSOs that participated in the survey represent work at different levels, from grassroots local organisations to nationwide operating NGOs, which are engaged in advocacy and oversight activities as well as in implementing humanitarian and development projects.

Box 1 Diagnostic Tools for National Evaluation Systems

A first step towards strengthening national M&E systems is gaining a thorough understanding of their structures and dynamics. Several diagnostic tools support such analysis, such as the INCE and the MESA.

The **INCE** is an index developed by a broad coalition of partners in the Latin America and Caribbean region, led by the World Food Programme and DEval. It aims to involve a range of governmental and non-governmental actors in reflecting on the state of evaluation in a country. Data is collected collaboratively from public institutions, academia, development partners and Voluntary Organisations for Professional Evaluation (VOPEs), enabling a pluralistic system perspective. The INCE assesses national evaluation systems across five dimensions: institutional structure, evaluation offer, quality of evaluations, multi-agent spaces and use of evaluations (INCE, 2025).

The **MESA** tool, developed by the Global Evaluation Initiative (GEI), offers a comprehensive framework for analysing planning, budgeting, monitoring, reporting and evaluation processes. It also examines the use of evidence in policy making, with the aim of informing Evaluation Capacity Development (ECD) strategies (GEI, 2022).

Several challenges arose during data collection and analysis for this discussion paper. As this paper focuses on the state of Ukraine, it is important to acknowledge the limitations imposed by the ongoing full-scale invasion and the temporarily occupied territories. These areas are inaccessible, and reliable information or updates are limited.

Although the document analysis was limited by fragmented information and restricted access under martial law, triangulation with stakeholder interviews and a validation workshop helped to mitigate this. A potential bias could arise from the small number of interviews (n=5) caused by a challenging security situation and limited access to stakeholders due to continued war-related restrictions; this was partially addressed by incorporating insights from the validation workshop with M&E professionals and through extensive analysis of secondary literature, including reports from development partners, CSOs and academic literature. However, broader stakeholder engagement could have deepened insights into organisational culture and the evaluation system. The selected combination of primary and secondary data seemed appropriate to the contextual conditions of the ongoing war and the scope of this discussion paper (see Box 6 for reflections on the mapping exercise).

1.3 Structure

The discussion paper is structured as follows: **Chapter 2** presents a theoretical discussion on the challenges of evidence-based decision making and the development of national evaluation systems and capacities in fragile and conflict-affected states (2.1). It also explores the opportunities offered by the EU accession process as a potential driver for institutional reforms (2.2). **Chapter 3** introduces the case study of Ukraine, beginning with an overview of the country's political and socio-economic context, the legal background of its M&E system, and the key actors involved in that system. This is followed by a descriptive-analytical case study that examines the current state of Ukraine's M&E system and capacities. This part of the discussion paper is mainly based on empirical research conducted by members of the UEA. Chapter 3 primarily addresses sub-question (1), while discussion of questions (2) and (3) is developed throughout both Chapter 2 and Chapter 3, from both a theoretical and an empirical perspective, in relation to Ukraine and in a more general context. **Chapters 4 and 5** present the conclusions: Section 4.1 summarises the key findings from the case study while section 4.2 provides entry points for strengthening evidence-based decision making in Ukraine. Finally, Chapter 5 concludes by exploring the broader implications of evidence-based decision making in fragile and conflict-affected states.

2. THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This chapter explores theoretical considerations drawn from two strands of practice-oriented literature in the field of international relations: evidence-based decision making in fragile and conflict-affected states, and the EU enlargement process. It addresses two of the sub-questions from a theoretical perspective – first, by examining how armed conflict and fragility influence evidence-based decision making more broadly, and national evaluation systems more specifically; and second, by analysing the role of external drivers – particularly the EU – in supporting the development of such systems.

The analysis begins with a brief definition of the key concepts, state fragility and armed conflict, which are central to the broader debates in which this discussion paper is situated. This is followed by a discussion of the main findings around the role of evidence in conflict-affected contexts and in the EU enlargement process.

2.1 Evidence-Based Decision Making in Fragile and Conflict-Affected States

In international policy circles, it is common practice to address fragility and conflict in tandem – frequently under the umbrella of “fragile and conflict-affected states” (UNDP, 2016; World Bank Group, 2020). Fragility and armed conflict are conceptually distinct, yet closely linked – and often reinforce one another in reality. While fragility can exacerbate conflict, for instance through structural injustices, armed conflict can, in turn, further increase instability (BMZ, 2024; World Bank Group, 2020). At the same time, there is an emphasis on context sensitivity and recognizing that each situation is shaped by distinct conditions (CDA, 2016; Hassnain et al., 2021; Wolff et al., 2020). In contexts marked by fragility or armed conflict, the international community actively engages in peacebuilding as well as reconstruction and recovery efforts that aim to address these multifaceted challenges for development.

State fragility is a multidimensional concept that encompasses both narrow and broad definitional approaches. Narrow definitions typically concentrate on specific dimensions such as political instability, whereas broader conceptualizations also account for social, economic, environmental and other factors. The OECD's relatively broad framework, States of Fragility (OECD, 2025b), refers to a spectrum of risks that threaten state stability. According to this framework, fragility arises from the interaction between a state's exposure to risks and its insufficient institutional capacity to manage, absorb or mitigate those risks. Similarly, the Fragile States Index adopts a multidimensional approach, incorporating indicators related to cohesion, economic, political, social and cross-cutting dimensions (The Fund for Peace, 2017).

When focusing on statehood, fragility can be understood as a deficit in one or more core state functions – that is, authority, capacity and legitimacy (Faust et al., 2023; IDOS, 2024; Wencker and Verspohl, 2019, Ziaja et al., 2019), see also Figure 2. A lack of authority refers to the absence of a legitimate physical power's exclusive monopoly over a specific territory. Capacity relates to the state's ability to establish and enforce binding rules for society as a whole and to deliver essential public services. Legitimacy reflects the degree to which state institutions and practices are accepted as appropriate and justified by the population. This functional understanding of fragility allows structural challenges to statehood to be identified across different country contexts. Such frameworks offer a valuable lens for critically examining the functions of the state, which is pivotal for effective policy making. Rather than focusing solely on acute cases, crises or conflict situations, this conceptualises deficiencies in statehood as multidimensional and structural in nature (Wencker and Verspohl, 2019). Indices concerned with statehood and fragility mostly refrain from binary categorizations. Rather, they adopt a continuum-based approach, assessing all countries globally on the premise that fragility is a phenomenon that manifests to varying degrees across all states.

In this regard, Ukraine is not uniformly defined as a fragile state; rather, it shows deficiencies in specific dimensions – particularly authority and legitimacy – while demonstrating resilience and functionality in others, especially amid the challenges of full-scale interstate war. For example, the Fund for Peace ranked

Ukraine 22nd in its Fragile States Index, assigning it a score of 93.1 and categorizing it as “alert” in 2024.¹³ The OECD (OECD, 2025b) lists 61 contexts with high and extreme fragility; Ukraine is not among them. Meanwhile, the German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) adopts another approach by categorizing countries worldwide and employing a concept of “constellations of state fragility” to prevent overly simplistic classifications that obscure substantial differences between states (Lorch et al., 2024; Ziaja, 2025; Ziaja et al., 2019). Recent data from IDOS indicates that, prior to the full-scale invasion, Ukraine was predominantly classified within the semi-functional state cluster. States in this group have medium scores across all dimensions of statehood. Findings suggest that Ukraine’s state capacities have been relatively stable, averaging around 0.7 on a scale from 0 to 1. A significant decline in authority occurred in 2014, reflecting the onset of war in the eastern parts of Ukraine. From 2016 to 2021, authority remained at a lower level, around 0.5. During the same period, legitimacy ratings ranged between 0.5 and 0.6 (Lorch et al., 2024; Ziaja, 2025). This assessment mirrors challenges to rule of law and the separation of powers, institutional trust, civil liberties and corruption (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024; Freedom House, 2025). Since 2022, however, Ukraine has predominantly been classified as a low-authority state, with authority falling to 0 and legitimacy declining to approximately 0.4.

Figure 2 Concept of Fragility: Core State Functions and Deficiencies

Source: DEval, own illustration based on Max Weber’s concept of the state (see Faust et al. (2023), IDOS (2024), and Ziaja et al. (2019)).

In this paper, IDOS’ approach is followed, with Ukraine being understood as a state demonstrating deficiencies in the three dimensions of fragility to varying extents, primarily in terms of authority and legitimacy. While Ukraine’s state capacities are relatively strong, this is nevertheless an important factor that must be considered in light of the war (see section 3.1).

Armed conflict and war are commonly defined by quantitative thresholds of battle-related deaths within a calendar year – 25 fatalities for armed conflict and 1,000 for war (Uppsala University, 2025). In this way, an armed conflict is defined as a situation involving a contested incompatibility between parties, in which armed force is employed. Established typologies commonly classify violent conflicts based on the nature of violence

¹³ Compared with 2014: rank 113, 67.2; 2021: rank 91, 69.6 (warning).

and the involvement of state actors – distinguishing, for example, between interstate, intrastate and internationalised conflicts, or one-sided political violence. However, some approaches adopt more comprehensive criteria, incorporating additional defining characteristics such as conflict dynamics, key issues of contention and the composition of the warring parties.¹⁴ More generally, the term “conflict” refers to a relationship between at least two parties in which one party’s interests are constrained by the actions of the other; however, not every conflict escalates into violence. War, by contrast, denotes a high-intensity, organised armed conflict between states or population groups (Berghof Foundation, 2019; Heidelberg Institute for International Conflict Research, 2025; Uppsala University, 2025). Based on these definitions, the Russian full-scale invasion of Ukraine is an interstate war with high intensity, involving an aggressor and an attacked state (ACLED, 2025; Heidelberg Institute for International Conflict Research, 2023), where a major power in the international system is pursuing territorial expansion and the subjugation of another state through regime change (ACLED, 2025; Davies et al., 2023; Heidelberg Institute for International Conflict Research, 2023). Although political violence emerged in 2014, when Russia occupied and subsequently annexed Crimea and war broke out in the Donbas, the full-scale invasion of Ukraine marked a significant escalation in the course of events (Uppsala University, 2025). The Uppsala Conflict Data Program estimates that between 2022 and 2024, there were 243,624 battle-related fatalities in Ukraine (Uppsala University, 2025).

Armed conflict, fragility and crisis present significant challenges to evidence-based decision making for both national governments and international partners supporting development and peace. Past international civilian engagements have illustrated these challenges, which have become prevalent in international peacebuilding, recovery and reconstruction, highlighting the need for stronger consideration of and engagement with the topic of evidence orientation and learning in these settings. The evaluations of Germany’s civilian engagement in Iraq and Afghanistan by DEval and others underscore these challenges, as do further studies addressing engagement in fragile and conflict-affected contexts (DEval et al., 2023; Hartmann et al., 2021; see also Hartmann et al., 2022, 2023; Atal et al., 2023; Mielke and Nachtwei, 2024; SIGAR, 2023; Tull, 2024). Evidence-based decision making has been hampered by several factors, such as pressure to respond to international or national imperatives and the lack of a learning-oriented organisational culture among development partners. Nevertheless, the availability of evidence remains crucial for steering and guiding policy change. The evaluations conducted by DEval and others also found that management and steering of international support was primarily output-oriented, with a lack of impact orientation (DEval et al., 2023; Hartmann et al., 2022, 2023). The data generated was often insufficient to inform strategic management decisions. Despite the existence of common platforms and general structures, challenges in terms of international coherence and ownership towards common goals were also evident. Moreover, the availability of appropriate, context-specific information is a fundamental prerequisite for effective aid (Anderson, 2001). The joint ministerial evaluation of the German government’s civil engagement in Afghanistan points out that the overall international engagement plausibly contributed to unintended effects stemming from a dilemma existent within the Afghan context: enormous financial flows intended to meet the country’s vast needs encountered weak institutions with limited absorption capacities, thereby contributing to, among other things, persistent imported inflation and structurally fuelling corruption (DEval et al., 2023; see also Hassan, 2023).

Over the past decade, international development partners and the evaluation community have increasingly focused on evaluation in fragile and conflict-affected contexts, acknowledging the unique challenges these environments pose to good evaluation practice (Hassnain et al., 2021). Political, logistical, ethical and methodological challenges have been widely recognised. Other factors, such as instability, weak institutions, limited state capacities and lack of political will have also been shown to affect planning and implementation of evaluations, as well as usage of results (Better Evaluation Knowledge, 2025; Faust et al., 2023). However,

14 Such as those from the Armed Conflict Location and Event Data (ACLED) Project and the Heidelberg Institute for International Conflict Research.

research on the role of national evaluation systems and capacities for evidence-based decision making, learning and accountability in situations of fragility and conflict remains limited (Better Evaluation Knowledge, 2024; Hassnain et al., 2021). Some states affected by fragility and armed conflict¹⁵ are covered in studies of national evaluation systems, such as Madagascar (MESA) and Mexico (INCE). Furthermore, for example the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) conducted a “baseline study” with 42 country profiles on national evaluation capacities in 2015 (such as Afghanistan, Lebanon and Kenya) (UNDP, 2015). These studies, despite reflecting significant disparities in governance and capacity, identify common challenges such as restricted access to data and specific areas (Rajab, 2021; Rosenstein, 2015), as well as limited national M&E resources (Better Evaluation Knowledge, 2024; Rajab, 2021). These challenges are intensified by a lack of human capital, resulting from displacement and the disruption of education systems. Additional challenges include the absence of formal evaluation policies and the effects of practices commonly applied in international co-operation, such as the continued existence of skill gaps resulting from reliance on external evaluation capacities.

Few studies systematically consider the role of fragility, armed conflict and crises, so a deeper understanding of national evaluation systems in these contexts will provide valuable insights into how state and policy-making processes function and adapt. Strengthening evidence-based public decision making in fragile and conflict-affected states can contribute to different key purposes: first, national M&E systems are a component of the policy cycle and are therefore inherently connected with the policy-making process, which means that evidence has the potential to enhance good governance. In an environment where transparency is limited and the government lacks legitimacy, reliable evidence can serve as a counterweight, promoting more accountable, inclusive and effective policy making, and fostering society-state relations (OECD, 2025b; World Bank Group, 2024). Second, in the context of international co-operation, investing in national evaluation systems and capacities fits with the Aid Effectiveness Agenda's emphasis on ownership and coherence, by aligning development partners' approaches with shared goals and indicators (OECD, 2005). This paradigm is not an end in itself but can also help strengthen national institutions by enabling them to more effectively fulfil their core functions. Therefore, a greater focus on harmonizing with national systems also promotes a partner-oriented approach in international co-operation, maximizing the sustainable benefits of support for the respective countries (ODI Global, 2004; Rogerson, 2005). Third, leveraging local evaluation expertise and perspectives can enhance mutual learning and evaluation quality, for instance. Further, a greater evidence base allows for assessments of the effectiveness of public policies – an aspect that is particularly important, considering substantial financial aid flows and numerous pressing needs – both in terms of accountability and the need for learning.

2.2 Enhancing National Evaluation Systems and Capacities in the Context of EU Enlargement

Since Ukraine's EU accession negotiations opened and its EU candidate status was granted, the country has intensified its reform process to strengthen its governance system (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024) based on a revised EU enlargement methodology (EC, 2020). The EU accession process places considerable emphasis on enhancing administrative capacity development and institutional reform (Stockmann et al., 2020). In addition, the EU's requirements regarding M&E systems are seen as an external driver for establishing and fostering national M&E systems and capacities (Stockmann et al., 2020). M&E plays a central role in the EU enlargement process; in particular, the EU obliges candidate countries to report on the implementation progress of EU-funded programmes. One of the key instruments supporting candidate countries in aligning with the EU *acquis* is the Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance (IPA), formerly known as the Phare Programme. This instrument is designed to enhance administrative capacities through financial and technical

15 Following established indices to measure fragility and conflict: ACLED on armed conflict; Fragile State Index and Constellations of State Fragility for fragile statehood. Categorization differs depending on the indicators and understanding of these two concepts.

assistance across all sectors, thereby facilitating institutional reforms and preparing countries for EU membership. For the period from 2021 to 2027, the IPA III aims to leverage socio-economic reforms through a policy-driven approach, aligning potential candidate countries with EU standards and values (EC, n.d.). Like previous programming, the IPA III addresses monitoring on strategic, sector and action levels. Through the implementation of the EU Structural and Cohesion Funds, in particular, rigorous oversight and accountability is required.

Comparative studies on the impact of EU accession processes – and their potential role as drivers for strengthening evaluation capacities – remain scarce, even though the integration of monitoring, evaluation and learning practices is increasingly recognised as a pillar of governance (EC, 2016) and a requirement in the EU enlargement process. Past enlargement processes have shown that a lack of established M&E systems and culture has a negative impact on candidate countries' decision making and reform implementation (EC, 2016) and, if external pressure is low, the likelihood of establishing such systems is limited. Further, risks exist, including that evaluations may be solely used for legitimizing interventions, rather than for policy reforms – particularly in highly uncertain environments (Højlund, 2014).

The available literature regarding the impact of the EU enlargement process on the strengthening of evaluation systems and capacities focuses primarily on the cases of Lithuania, Latvia, Poland, Romania and Bulgaria (Stockmann et al., 2020). The studies highlight that in these countries, the EU enlargement process acted as an external driving force for national evaluation systems (Martinaitis et al., 2019; Stockmann et al., 2020) – the EU enlargement process led to the establishment of dedicated evaluation units, the development of standardised methodologies and the gradual integration of M&E processes across government structures. Over time, the evaluation process for EU membership evolved into an established tool within the policy cycle of national decision making of public policies (Dvorak, 2010). However, the countries have differed considerably in their institutionalization of evaluation practices beyond the monitoring of EU funds. Lithuania, where the development of an evaluation system has moved towards an instrumental use for the improvement of policy implementation, can be seen as a best practice example (Martinaitis et al., 2019; Stockmann et al., 2020). The degree to which EU accession and candidate countries have shifted their focus from EU-funded programmes to more comprehensive policy making varies (Stockmann et al., 2020). In some countries, such as Lithuania and Poland, evaluation has evolved beyond a symbolic use (Martinaitis et al., 2019; Stockmann et al., 2020). In others, such as Latvia, Romania and Bulgaria, different challenges remain regarding the quality and strategic use of evaluation systems (Stockmann et al., 2020).

3. CASE STUDY: EVIDENCE-BASED DECISION MAKING IN UKRAINE

This chapter presents the analysis of the case of Ukraine that forms the empirical basis for this discussion paper. It examines the current state of Ukraine's evaluation system (sub-question 1) and explores the relevance of armed conflict (sub-question 2), recovery and reconstruction, and EU enlargement (sub-question 3) by using the models proposed by the INCE and MESA tools as a reference to describe and diagnose the capacities of the national evaluation system.

An evaluation system can be described through its institutional structures, processes and stakeholder engagement, as illustrated in Figure 3. This study focuses on governmental actors and CSOs and independent evaluators. Importantly, an evaluation system is always embedded in a broader context (see orange outline in Figure 3). Due to the importance of international actors in recovery, reconstruction and the EU accession process, they are also included in this analysis.

Figure 3 Components and Actors in National Evaluation Systems

Source: Retrieved from DEval (2025), own adaptation to the context.

Section 3.1 provides a brief country profile to set the current evaluation structures and capacities in context. Section 3.2 describes the main features of the M&E system, its capacities and actors in Ukraine. This includes the legal basis and state institutions as well as the role of non-state actors as highlighted in blue. Actors and structures related to Ukraine's recovery and reconstruction process, as well as the EU accession process with a focus on the recipient side, are also considered (sections 3.2.1-3.2.3). Section 3.2.4 sheds light on the quality and availability of public data, while section 3.2.5 focuses on evaluation skills and existing capacity development measures, referring to components of the evaluation system highlighted in the orange boxes (dashed lines). The impact of war is integrated throughout the analysis.

3.1 Context of Ukraine

Ukraine is a unitary state located in Eastern Europe. With a territory of 603,550 square kilometres, it is the second-largest country in Europe, and its land borders span 5,581 kilometres (CIA, 2025).¹⁶ Ukraine is a parliamentary-presidential republic (Federal Foreign Office, 2025) where citizens directly elect the president, members of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine (VRU, the parliament) and local councils.¹⁷ It has a multi-party system, with several parties competing at elections. The president of Ukraine serves as the head of state and is responsible for safeguarding the country's sovereignty and territorial integrity, as well as upholding the Constitution of Ukraine and ensuring the protection of human and civil rights. According to the Constitution, the president has the right to nominate the prime minister and the ministers of defence and foreign affairs, for parliamentary approval. The president has the authority to influence all three branches of government and exercises certain executive powers. Meanwhile, the prime minister, who is nominated by the president and appointed with the consent of the VRU, serves as the head of government. The prime minister oversees the activities of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine (CMU) and nominates its comprising ministers for confirmation.¹⁸ The CMU is the main executive body and is accountable to both the president and the VRU. Its activities are supported by a permanent Secretariat, which provides administrative, policy-related and analytical assistance to the cabinet, its committees and senior officials. The central legislative authority is the VRU, a unicameral parliament composed of 450 members elected through a mixed electoral system. The powers of the VRU regarding parliamentary oversight of government performance, namely the CMU, are enshrined in the Constitution of Ukraine (see Article 85, Part 1, Clause 13).

Local self-government in Ukraine is organised into a hierarchical system comprised of oblasts, rayons and hromadas.¹⁹ Local entities exercise authority either directly or through elected local councils and their executive bodies. Since 2014, Ukraine has undertaken a comprehensive decentralisation reform aimed at devolving political, administrative and fiscal powers to the local level (Krawchenko, 2023).²⁰ As a result, local authorities have gained increased responsibilities – not only for delivering services but also for implementing and monitoring local policies. Substantial reforms of the public administration have been undertaken since 2014 (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024). In particular, increased digitalization has enhanced administrative efficiency and citizen access to services. Still, strengthening institutions and improving administration – including by addressing challenges such as limited personnel capacities, high fluctuation and administrative complexity – remain areas for further development (Vavreniuk et al., 2021; World Bank Group, 2021). Despite the full-scale invasion, the public administration has remained functional, demonstrating high resilience (OECD, 2024).

Ukraine's modern statehood has been shaped by a complex and contested history. After briefly declaring independence in 1917-1921 during the collapse of imperial powers, Ukraine was incorporated into the Soviet Union, where it remained until declaring independence in 1991 (Brand Ukraine, 2022). Ukraine's subsequent

16 The figures refer to the entire territory of Ukraine, including the territories that were illegally annexed by Russia since 2014.

17 The presidential elections are held every five years. However, the elections originally scheduled for 2024 did not take place due to the imposition of martial law prohibiting elections under Ukrainian legislation. The parliamentary elections are held every four years and are scheduled for October 2025.

18 An important exception to this nomination authority are the minister for defence and the minister for foreign affairs, who are nominated by the president.

19 Oblasts represent the highest regional administrative division, roughly corresponding with a province. They are responsible for overseeing education, healthcare, infrastructure and regional development. Just below the oblasts are the rayons. Rayons are comparable to districts and are responsible coordinating government activities across a smaller area. Oblasts and rayons exercise authority either directly or through elected local councils and their executive bodies. Additionally, councils at the oblast and rayon level represent the shared interests of multiple territorial communities. Hromadas are the smallest form of territorial sub-division and are responsible for service delivery in the areas of education, utilities, and local infrastructure (All-Ukrainian Association of Local Governments, n.d.; Ukrainska Pravda Media Plus, 2020; VRU, 1996).

20 Ukraine's decentralization strategy was outlined in the 2014 Concept Framework of the Reform of Local Self-Government and the Territorial Organisation of Power in Ukraine.

transition from communism to capitalism was characterised by political cleavages and intense conflicts over its political and economic direction (Ishchenko and Zhuravlev 2021). Key moments in Ukraine's post-Soviet transformation include the Orange Revolution (2004-2005) and the Revolution of Dignity (2013-2014), both of which reaffirmed Ukrainian citizens' democratic aspirations and orientation towards Europe. Russia's annexation of Crimea and occupation of parts of Donbas in March 2014 marked the beginning of the Russian war against Ukraine. In the same year, the Association Agreement (AA), including a Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area was signed between the EU, its member states and Ukraine (EU, 2014), promoting reforms towards EU standards and practices. Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 finally broke international diplomatic frameworks, such as the Minsk agreements.²¹ In 2022, the European Council granted Ukraine candidate status for EU accession, leading to the country's need to comply by adopting the *acquis communautaire* – in addition to the AA – and by introducing robust M&E practices across its government (Mrak and Zuber, 2023).

Since Ukraine's independence from the Soviet Union in 1991, the country has made significant progress in its democratic transformation; however, democratic progress remains uneven. Index-based assessments reflect this ambiguity: Ukraine is classified as "partly free" (Freedom House, 2025)²² and as an "electoral autocracy" (Fröhlich, 2023; Nord et al., 2025; see also the Electoral Democracy Index in Figure 4 by V-Dem). Ukraine's state formation has been characterised by ups and downs of both state capacity and democratic accountability (Fröhlich, 2023). Despite periods of transformation, the country's institutional development has been hindered by corruption, rent-seeking business and political elites, and weaknesses in the checks and balances system, specifically with regards to the independence of the judiciary (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024; DGO et al., 2023; Kakachia et al., 2021; Nord et al., 2025). Reforms to fight corruption and improve governance and accountability have been initiated, though progress has been inconsistent (Savoy and Lohsen, 2022; World Bank Group, 2021). Government effectiveness, which the World Bank defines as the quality of public service provision and bureaucracy, the competence of civil servants, and the quality of policy formulation and implementation, has increased in recent years. However, it remains at a low level.²³ Despite some improvements, Ukraine still performs below the average among the EU candidate countries and generally low on the Corruption Perceptions Index. In 2024, the country ranked 105th out of 179 countries, with a Corruption Perceptions Index score of 35 out of 100 (Transparency International, 2025). Similarly, the V-Dem indicator illustrates an increase in bribery and corruption since 2012; see Figure 4.

The full-scale invasion has led to a deterioration in political and civil liberties, putting the democratic reform process under scrutiny. In response to the invasion, the Ukrainian government decreed martial law, which had negative implications for transparency, elections, political rights and civil liberties. For example, the parliamentary elections scheduled for October 2024 have been postponed until after martial law is lifted (EC, 2023). Men aged between 18 and 60 are generally not allowed to leave the country, and access to data and information is often more challenging (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024). Further, the government imposed restrictions on freedom of expression, including on journalism, and on freedom of association, with peaceful assemblies not allowed due to security concerns (USAID et al., 2023b). However, since the full-scale invasion, business oligarchs' control over media outlets has been weakened, and anti-corruption measures have increased (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024). Effective reconstruction in the public sector will require not only enhanced absorptive capacity but also improved systems and processes (World Bank et al., 2025).

21 The ceasefire agreement Minsk II led to a sharp decrease in hostilities; however, many parts of the agreement were only partially implemented. Between 2014 and 2015, the Minsk accord (ceasefire) was signed by Russia, Germany, Ukraine and France. In February 2022, Russia launched a full-scale invasion of Ukraine, definitively breaking the agreement.

22 Crimea and the eastern part of Donbas are separately categorised as "not free".

23 The information provided on "government effectiveness" is based on the Government Effectiveness indicator by the World Bank Group. The estimate provides the score for each country on this indicator, ranging from approximately -2.5 to 2.5. For further information, see World Bank (2023).

Figure 4 Democratic Transformation Trend in Ukraine (1991-2024)

Source: DEval, own Illustration based on V-Dem (V-Dem Institute, n.d.).

After continuous growth since 2015 (World Bank, 2024), Ukraine's GDP was affected by the broader consequences of the onset of Russia's full-scale invasion in 2022 (EC, 2024b). On a macroeconomic scale, two primary invasion-related factors have negatively affected the country: the ongoing destruction of productive capital and the disruption of economic processes (World Bank et al., 2025). Despite the war, Ukraine's economy advanced from lower-middle income status to upper-middle in 2023, when it reached its highest-ever GDP per capita (4,936 euros) (EC, 2024b). This recovery is largely attributed to reconstruction-related investment, particularly in construction, which grew by 24.6%, as well as capital spending, which increased by 52.9%. Nevertheless, Ukraine's economic gains are tempered by population decline, which has fallen more than 15% since the full-scale invasion began, and high inflation, particularly in domestic goods and services. The service sector has remained relatively resilient, functioning as the dominant contributor to GDP (at 61.4% of GDP in 2023), followed by industry (18.8%) and agriculture (7.4%), though all sectors have lost relative importance since 2014 (World Bank, 2024). The war has redefined Ukraine's international trade, cutting off Russia and shifting exports primarily to Poland, Romania, China, Turkey and Spain. Imports, meanwhile, now come mainly from China, Poland, Germany, Turkey and the USA (OEC, n.d.). Financing needs are high due to the ongoing hostilities, with defence accounting for 32% of government expenditure in 2023 (World Bank et al., 2025).

Since the 2014 Euromaidan, Ukrainian civil society has emerged as a critical actor in governance reform and democratic accountability; CSOs have expanded in number and influence, particularly during crises such as COVID-19 and the ongoing war. Ukraine has a vibrant and diverse civil society sector: the Ukrainian State Statistics Service counted 99,556 public associations, 28,757 trade unions, 27,091 religious organisations, 26,846 charitable organisations, 2,212 unions of public associations, 1,762 self-organised bodies and 318 creative unions, as of 1 January 2023 (USAID et al., 2023b).²⁴ The regulative framework governing the

²⁴ Compared with 2019, the figures of officially registered CSOs were slightly lower, at 88,882 registered public associations, 1,718 unions of public associations, 26,347 religious organisations, 28,486 trade unions, 317 creative unions, 19,112 charitable organisations and 1,614 self-organised bodies (USAID et al., 2020).

activities of CSOs in Ukraine is based on several legislative acts.²⁵ There are no restrictions on providing foreign aid to CSOs (Krasnenko, 2025). The positive trend in the participatory environment since 2014 is also illustrated in Figure 4 above.

CSOs in Ukraine are active in a wide range of sectors, including human rights, education, sustainable development, culture and humanitarian aid. Since Russia's full-scale invasion, CSO activities have shifted towards humanitarian response and reconstruction (Krasnenko, 2025). Although the sustainability of CSOs has improved in recent years, constraints still exist due to limited domestic funding opportunities, making CSOs more dependent on development partners, and there are capacity gaps in management and strategic planning (ETF, 2021). Ukraine is characterised by strong civic engagement, and CSOs' advocacy capacities remain robust (USAID et al., 2020, 2023a). The ongoing EU accession process has opened new opportunities for Ukrainian CSOs, while increased alignment with EU policies has strengthened the regulatory and institutional frameworks in which CSOs operate and enhanced their role in shaping public policy.

3.2 National Evaluation System and Capacities in Ukraine

The following chapter describes the current national evaluation system and capacities in Ukraine. Section 3.2.1 outlines the existing legal framework and previous attempts to establish a national M&E policy. Section 3.2.2 focuses on structures and actors related to reconstruction, recovery and EU integration. Different important actors of the national evaluation system, their roles and the actual practices are then analysed in section 3.2.3, with a focus on state actors (the government, line ministries and the parliament) and non-state actors, such as civil society. Section 3.2.4 describes the state of available data. Section 3.2.5 deals with capacity development measures and training in M&E.

3.2.1 Legal Basis for M&E of Public Policies

Ukraine has not yet established a comprehensive legislative framework for M&E of public policies. Previous attempts to formalise M&E have been unsuccessful. Each state policy sector is subject to its own set of regulations, and the legislation pertaining to M&E in regional policy is among the most advanced in Ukraine. Since Russia's full-scale invasion, demands for M&E have increased to facilitate recovery and reconstruction. Concurrently, the processes of EU accession have led to new legislative initiatives.

Like in other post-Soviet countries, Ukraine operates within a highly formalistic legal culture, where public administration is strongly rule-based and action takes place after being explicitly authorised by law (Chernykh, 2023; Khadzhyradieva et al., 2020; OECD, 2024). At the time of writing, at least two attempts to introduce an overarching legislation regulating M&E of public policy in recent years have not been successful. The first initiative was in 2011, when Draft Law No. 9407 "On State Strategic Planning" was submitted to the parliament (VRU, 2011). It proposed state strategic planning documents, including mandatory M&E, with procedures to be defined by the government. While the draft law passed its first reading, it was ultimately discontinued during the second reading stage. The second attempt was made in 2017, when the Ministry of Economy drafted the Law "On State Strategic Planning" to strengthen Ukraine's strategic planning system (Ministry of Economy of Ukraine, 2017). The aim of the legislation was to establish a legal and organisational framework for a cohesive state strategic planning system to support Ukraine's development. It defined a set of documents, including goals, strategic directions, priorities, tasks and measures of state policy, which would serve as the basis for budget planning. The law also outlined procedures for the M&E of these documents,

²⁵ It is based on the "Law on State Registration of Legal Entities, Individual Entrepreneurs and CSOs", the "Law on Public Associations" from 2012, and the "2016 Order of the Ministry of Justice on Approval of the Procedure for State Registration of Legal Entities, Entrepreneurs and Entities Forming Non-Legal Entities", and is guaranteed by the Constitution of Ukraine and international treaties signed by Ukraine (ETF, 2021; USAID et al., 2020).

with the CMU being tasked with establishing procedures for developing strategies, including M&E of the effectiveness of their implementation. However, the draft law was not submitted to the VRU and, consequently, has not been enacted into law (UNDP and EU, 2023; Vavreniuk et al., 2021). Due to these unsuccessful attempts to establish a regulatory framework for public evaluation (mainly because of the non-priority of the issue), M&E-related provisions are dispersed across various laws and subordinate regulatory acts, which has led to fragmented and inconsistent practices.

The Government of Ukraine develops state target programmes to facilitate the implementation of state policy in priority areas of national development, specific economic sectors and administrative-territorial units. These programmes are intended to ensure material, technical and other resources are efficiently allocated and utilised, as well as to co-ordinate the efforts of central and local executive authorities, enterprises, institutions and organisations in addressing critical developmental challenges. They are funded by the State Budget of Ukraine and are systematically aligned in terms of implementation timelines, designated executors and resource planning. However, the Law of Ukraine “On State Target Programmes” includes no provisions for M&E (VRU, 2004), even though such programmes are among the primary instruments of the respective state policies. This law mentions only the evaluation of expected results, programme efficiency and the targeted use of funds.

Although M&E-related provisions are dispersed across numerous regulations governing various policy areas, they do not form a coherent framework for effectively implementing M&E functions. An analysis of governmental and central executive body documents shows that sectoral policies with specific references to M&E do exist, such as with regards to social support programmes (Order, 2017, September 1) and within regional development.²⁶ Adopted in 2015, the Law of Ukraine “On the Principles of State Regional Policy” (VRU, 2015) has a dedicated section on the M&E of regional policy. It mandates the evaluation of the effectiveness, efficiency and impact of development strategies at the national, regional and local levels, as well as the use of public funds allocated for their implementation. Evaluations must draw from various sources, including monitoring data, statistical data, results of expert assessments, surveys, and evaluations by non-governmental organisations (NGOs), research institutions and international experts. The law stipulates both mid-term evaluations for potential adjustments and final evaluations of the strategies to assess whether policy goals have been achieved. In March 2024, a corresponding procedure was approved in accordance with the Law “On the Principles of State Regional Policy” (Articles 24 and 26) (CMU, 2024a), largely maintaining the same provisions as the previous law. For example, the State Strategy for Regional Development of Ukraine and its action plan should be monitored and evaluated according to the respective laws (Articles 8, 9, 24) (CMU, 2023a). The government body responsible for M&E is the Ministry for Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine, although the analysis confirmed that independent evaluation of the State Strategy for Regional Development of Ukraine has not taken place.

To conclude, establishing an evaluation policy framework has been rather low on the government's agenda. The lack of implementation of regulations for the M&E of strategic planning documents at the national level can be attributed to limited recognition of the importance of M&E among policy makers, including members of the VRU. While the failure of draft laws in parliament is not uncommon, the unsuccessful attempts in 2011 and 2017 highlight a persistent lack of awareness regarding the significance of M&E. The broader political context shows a general lack of coherence within the Ukrainian legal doctrine; the country has no clear, consistent approaches to how regulatory policy and planning should be interconnected. Without a legal enforcement mechanism that could impose sanctions for non-compliance, M&E is often neglected or conducted at a superficial level. The persisting legalistic understanding in post-Soviet administration requires a regulatory framework to guide practical implementation. To advance the debate, Ukraine's exemplary adoption of the procedures in state regional policy – despite remaining challenges in practical

26 A list of other regulatory acts governing M&E is provided in Annex 7.1.

implementation – can be seen as a modest yet positive step towards the institutionalization of M&E within the strategic planning system, because it formally anchors the importance of M&E in legislation. Since the beginning of Russia's full-scale invasion in 2022, Ukraine's legislative priorities have shifted towards addressing more immediate and urgent needs in defence and security, while compounding existing challenges have arisen in public administration, particularly regarding limited financial and human resources. Since the invasion, there have been no local attempts at the national level to strengthen the legal framework regarding M&E of public policies. However, recovery and reconstruction efforts and the EU accession process have recently initiated a substantial reform process, in which M&E aspects are a component.

3.2.2 Reconstruction and Recovery and the EU Accession Process

The EU AA, which came into effect before the EU accession process, has already led to Ukraine creating new governmental practices in monitoring the progress towards meeting the EU's criteria. Further, the recovery and reconstruction process and increased engagement of development partners have resulted in the requirement to monitor war damages, identify needs for recovery and reconstruction, and provide an overview of the fulfilment of agreed reforms through joint matrices. It is too early to assess whether they have resulted in enhanced M&E co-ordination, practices and awareness among governmental administration. Yet, the recently established structure and number of actors indicate a high level of complexity regarding responsibilities and co-ordination efforts.

The EU accession process and the extensive international assistance for Ukraine's recovery and reconstruction both serve as significant external drivers for public sector reform, particularly in relation to strengthening evidence-based decision making, including M&E practices. Both processes, especially the alignment with the EU *acquis*, necessitate Ukraine to establish new institutional structures and functions or adapt existing ones. These processes incentivise, and in some cases require, the development of a more coherent national M&E system and associated administrative capacities. This section outlines some of the key policy frameworks and institutional actors involved in Ukraine's reconstruction, recovery and EU accession process from a national viewpoint.

In 2017, the CMU adopted the Regulation on Planning, Monitoring, and Evaluation of the EU-Ukraine AA Implementation (CMU, 2017a) and, later, the Action Plan for the Implementation of the AA until 2027 (CMU, 2017b). The AA of 2017 and the monitoring process of its implementation form the basis of the EU accession process (Vavreniuk et al., 2021). However, the EU Accession Report assesses the implementation of the entire EU "*acquis communautaire*", rather than focusing on specific parts of it, as in the case of the AA. On the Ukrainian side, in 2017 the Government Office for Coordination on European and Euro-Atlantic Integration, under the direction of the Office of the Deputy Prime Minister for European and Euro-Atlantic integration, was established within the CMU. This office is tasked with, among other things, assessing the implementation of initiatives outlined in the Action Plan and developing recommendations and proposals on the AA implementation (CMU, n.d.a). Further, it is responsible for oversight of the EU accession negotiations. As part of its monitoring exercises, it publishes a progress report on the implementation of the AA (CMU, n.d.a). The implementation status is assessed based on an analysis of quarterly reports submitted by executive authorities (CMU, n.d.b).

On 1 March 2024, the Ukraine Facility – an EU instrument designed to support Ukraine in addressing the consequences of Russia's aggression and advancing its path toward EU accession – entered into force. Effective through 2027 and offering up to 50 billion euros in stable financial aid, it mandates comprehensive strategies and action plans for Ukraine, ensuring adherence to EU-backed reforms (EC, 2024a). To guarantee effective oversight, the European Commission is working on establishing a framework agreement that details the management, monitoring, evaluation and auditing of funds.

In November 2024, the Government of Ukraine approved the Procedure for Management, Monitoring and Control of Expenditures under the Ukraine Facility (CMU, 2024b). This procedure introduced a results-based

management system for strategic planning and M&E²⁷ to oversee the further implementation of the Ukraine Facility. The State Audit Service, meanwhile, will exercise state financial control over the expenditures envisaged for the implementation of the Ukraine Facility Plan, particularly those involving public procurement, compensation payments and loans (CMU, 2024b).

The authority responsible for implementing and monitoring the Ukraine Facility is the National Coordinator, who acts as the point of contact for different EU offices (Government of Ukraine, 2024). A dedicated scoreboard will track Ukraine's progress, while regular dialogues with the European Parliament and reports from an independent audit board – located in Brussels and supported by a secretariat in Kyiv – will provide transparent updates and recommendations on the Ukraine Facility's implementation (EU, 2024a). This structure should provide Ukraine with a clear mechanism for monitoring and accountability in its use of support funds (EC, 2024c).

In June 2024, the CMU adopted the Resolution “On Monitoring the Implementation of the Reforms Matrix”, which designates the Ukrainian Ministry of Finance as responsible for monitoring the implementation of the Reforms Matrix, and calls for other ministries and central bodies to update their respective information on a monthly basis. The Reforms Matrix is an analytical tool designed to support effective decision making and manage the reform implementation process for Ukraine's recovery and reconstruction. It systematises the conditions and recommendations of Ukraine's international partners in key sectors (Ministry of Finance of Ukraine, 2024). Against the backdrop of the “Build Back Better” principle and the goal of advancing both recovery and reconstruction and EU accession in tandem, the Reforms Matrix consolidates various agreements and conditions with different international partners. It covers over 200 reforms agreed upon in arrangements with the EU, under the Ukraine Facility Plan, a memorandum with the International Monetary Fund, and agreements with the World Bank. The Reforms Matrix enables tracking of Ukraine's overall progress based on over 500 indicators. A few indicators specifically relate to evaluation in different sectors, such as judiciary, economic development, regional development and public investments. For example, within the cluster on the fundamentals of the accession process, one target indicator is the provision of information for “effective functioning systems of coordination, M&E of the effectiveness” in the field of anti-corruption policies. In the same cluster, another target indicator stipulates the establishment of unified approaches to the “selection, evaluation and monitoring of investment projects, regardless of the sources of funding” (CMU, 2025). According to the website, the Reforms Matrix should enhance “accountability to the public and coordination with international partners, including the Ukraine Donor Platform” and “continuous monitoring” (CMU, 2025). The Ukraine Donor Platform was set up by the European Commission, alongside Ukraine and G7 partners, to support Ukraine's recovery and reconstruction process. Its main goal is to bring together development partners, as well as Ukrainian authorities, to prioritise and define Ukraine's strategic needs for the recovery and reconstruction process (EU, 2024b).

Within the CMU, the position of the Deputy Prime Minister for Restoration of Ukraine – Minister for Development Communities and Territories of Ukraine has been established, with responsibility for co-ordinating international assistance. The State Agency for Restoration and Infrastructure Development of Ukraine is a subordinated government body established in 2023 for technical co-ordination, such as optimizing work processes and co-ordinating the planning and implementation of reconstruction projects (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024; State Agency for Reconstruction and Development of Infrastructure of Ukraine, n.d.).

²⁷ Principles were developed within the framework of the ITA project “Support to Ukraine's Government Reforms” (SURGe). Through a series of reform projects, SURGe supports the Ukrainian government in making systems responsive to citizen needs, with a focus on the country's most vulnerable. This work extends to central government planning by developing capacities for results-based management, gender equality and social inclusion (Alinea, 2025).

3.2.3 Mapping of Important Actors in M&E in Ukraine

Ukraine's M&E landscape is shaped by a wide range of actors, including government institutions, parliament, CSOs, media, international development partners, private sector consultants, and professional networks. Each actor has a different role in the design, implementation, monitoring and advocacy of public policy evaluation, while their responsibilities and capacities vary. This section introduces these actors, outlines their institutional responsibilities and legal mandates, and assesses the current practices, capacities, and gaps in the M&E landscape in Ukraine.

Key Actors

State Actors

- **Government:** among Ukraine's government administration, the most important body for co-ordinating M&E practices is the CMU. Capacities for evidence-based decision making are low amongst government actors. The government does not commission independent evaluations, and no budgets are set aside for public policy evaluation.
- Ukraine's governance context permits each **ministry** to independently monitor and evaluate the development of the sectors; however, their M&E responsibility is not institutionalised across the line ministries in Ukraine. Instead, different approaches exist across different ministries. Any implemented activities mostly focus on compliance, accountability and control. The ministries do not have dedicated M&E departments, and internal capacities for conducting evaluations vary among line ministries but remain insufficient overall.
- **Parliament:** the VRU oversees the activities of the CMU through a variety of mechanisms. Nevertheless, improvements are needed in how effectively the government are held accountable. Whether a stronger monitoring role can be fulfilled is contingent on the clarity and measurability of objectives set by the government.

Non-State Actors

- **Civil society:** Ukrainian CSOs play an active role in monitoring various state policies, such as energy and environment. However, their engagement in evaluations remains limited, because other competing priorities and limited available resources discourage them from undertaking such activities.
- Further stakeholders in the national evaluation system include **private firms, consulting companies, research and marketing firms, academic institutions, independent evaluators, and the media**, all of which fulfil certain functions. Overall, many non-state professionals participate in M&E outside of governmental activities, albeit with varying capacities and scope. The private sector's capacity for policy and programme evaluation is primarily concentrated within branches of international consulting firms. Ukrainian consulting companies mainly focus on marketing and sociological research, providing ad hoc support to evaluations run by international organisations or companies. Academia and initiatives supported by development partners provide some training programmes, mainly focusing on entry-level education. Standardised training and certifications are not introduced. Many independent evaluators exist, with different backgrounds and capacities, some of which are united under the umbrella of the UEA. The UEA is the only officially registered VOPE in Ukraine. Although the UEA is active in the international arena, its organisational capacity is limited, and it operates more as a professional club than a fully functioning self-regulatory body. The media also plays an active role, particularly in investigative journalism.

3.2.3.1 Government Capacity for Evaluation Management and Co-ordination

Within the executive branch, the president, prime minister and CMU are responsible for setting national development priorities, adopting policy frameworks and overseeing implementation. The primary responsibility for formulating and implementing public policy lies with the CMU, led by the prime minister, and with the president, who shapes strategic direction and national priorities. However, the president's role in setting priorities for evidence orientation in public policies is very limited. As of December 2024, there is no co-ordinating body for evaluation at the governmental level in Ukraine.

In 2019, the government made some formal steps towards more coherent policy formulation and monitoring structures. The EU progress report assesses that the policy-making system is well established and that the CMU conducts “quality assurance and coordination of draft documents at the final stages of the process” (EC, 2023: 16). The new steps were accompanied by expanding the role of the CMU and included the introduction of new policy directorates: structural units responsible for public policy formulation, coordination and monitoring. However, these formal improvements, which were only completed recently, have not yet been translated into a functioning, institutionalised evaluation system. The establishment of the new directorates is assessed as incomplete: “By the end of 2022, less than 750 reform support posts had been filled out of 3,000 planned posts, with a declining trend in 2023” (EC, 2023: 17).

The monitoring of mid-term action plans and annual action plans is conducted ad hoc, with a focus on outputs measured by quantitative indicators – outcomes and impacts are not evaluated (EC, 2023, 2024a). This compliance-driven approach reflects the absence of an overall regulative framework, a lack of awareness of the meaning of the terminology “monitoring” and “evaluation”, and a lack of promotion of an enhanced functional understanding of the importance of evaluation in the policy cycle. For example, a notable discrepancy in assessing progress can be seen in the differences between the AA progress reports published by the European Commission and the respective report by the Ukrainian government. In Ukraine, the national assessment, published by the Deputy Prime Minister for European and Euro-Atlantic Integration, is based solely on quantitative indicators and determines a percentage of adopted or agreed documents or regulations in relation to the total AA. Using this method, Ukraine reached 77% of the required implementation in 2023. The EU, on the other hand, assesses progress on average through “some level of preparation”, which corresponds to about 40% of all progress efforts (Stewart, 2024). The use of international evaluation standards (by OECD and the United Nations Evaluation Group) at the governmental level is limited. The latest EU progress report assesses Ukraine’s capacities for evidence-based policy making as still “insufficient” (EC, 2024a). This gap becomes particularly evident in the legislative process: explanatory notes submitted by line ministries in support of draft legislative proposals frequently fail to meet the required standards, especially regarding cost estimates of draft policy initiatives and legal acts and implementation implications. In 2022, only 2 out of 28 policy documents approved by the CMU included information on implementation costs (EC, 2023). As a result, draft laws proposed in Ukraine are often inadequate or ineffective, particularly in areas where experience is limited (Kovaliv et al., 2022).

According to the EU assessment:

“The quality of explanatory notes and impact analysis accompanying legislative proposals is poor and should be improved. Information on the costing of policy documents and legislative acts is largely absent. The role of the government as an initiator of draft legislation continued to be limited, with most adopted draft legislation submitted by Members of Parliament (MPs).” (EC, 2024a: 25)

External evaluations of government activities and policies are permitted by different initiatives and regulatory documents that provide the foundational framework for evaluations. For instance, the Unified Procurement Vocabulary²⁸ includes consulting services on evaluation, and the Pulse of the Agreement is an online public system that monitors Ukraine’s progress in the AA (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024). However, a notable gap exists in the government between the established structures and the actual practice of conducting independent evaluations and capacities for evidence-based decision making (compare Box 2). As confirmed by interviewees, the government and ministries rarely commission independent external policy and programme evaluations. For example, although the Ministry for Development of Communities and

28 The National Classifier of Ukraine “Unified Procurement Dictionary” is designed to standardise the description of the subject of public procurement contracts, ensure greater transparency in procurement procedures for goods, works and services with public funds, create an effective competitive environment in the field of public procurement, and support the participation of domestic economic entities in tenders outside of Ukraine. The “Unified Procurement Dictionary” is harmonised with the European procurement dictionary, the Common Procurement Vocabulary.

Territories of Ukraine has published several internal monitoring reports on regional development, an external independent evaluation of the State Strategy of Regional Development for 2021-2027 – which had to be conducted within one year of its implementation (Ministry of Infrastructure of Ukraine, n.d.) – has not been carried out. The Ministry of Economy performs analyses of state target programmes, the most recent of which was conducted in 2020. This analysis focuses mainly on spendings of budgetary resources, much like an audit (Ministry of Economy of Ukraine, 2020).

Box 2 Government Commissioning of External Evaluations

In the Prozorro system, a public e-procurement system in Ukraine, most procurements under this code pertain to property valuation services, including real estate (Prozorro, n.d.; Transparency International Ukraine, n.d.). During interviews, stakeholders confirmed that no funds have specifically been allocated for evaluations beyond property valuation, and that there is no established practice of procuring external evaluation services. Procuring M&E services to assess government body performance is more of an exception than a norm. An analysis of procurements in the Prozorro system revealed a noteworthy example: the Uzhhorod City Council commissioned consulting services to evaluate the effectiveness in “public engagement” of its six structural units and to develop its draft communication strategy. However, this example remains an exception, underscoring the absence of a culture of external independent evaluations at the governmental level. The situation is further complicated by the generally limited budgets of governmental bodies and budgetary restrictions imposed during the war.

Other agencies and bodies working on enhancing transparency and accountability are the National Agency on Corruption Prevention (NACP) and the State Audit Service of Ukraine. The NACP is required to submit an annual report to the Public Council under it for review. The report is then published on the NACP's official website, along with the Public Council's conclusion. Meanwhile, the State Audit Service of Ukraine is a central executive body responsible for implementing state policy in the field of public financial control. Its mission is to execute state financial control aimed at assessing the effective, lawful, targeted, and efficient use and preservation of public financial resources. It seeks to achieve budget savings and provides recommendations to the Minister of Finance regarding the formation of state policy in public financial control. Its primary functions include monitoring and controlling public procurement, as well as conducting state financial audits. As the State Audit Service focuses primarily on financial control, its role in evaluation is rather limited (State Audit Service of Ukraine, 2024).

Interviewed government representatives acknowledged the importance of implementing M&E practices in governmental work. However, they emphasised factors such as a shortage of qualified personnel, a large volume of ongoing work and the need to address wartime challenges as the primary reasons preventing them from prioritizing the issue at this stage. A representative of one of the ministries stated: “The Ministry's funding is significantly constrained, and we fully acknowledge the needs and priorities of wartime. Therefore, at this time, the issue of increasing expenditures for administrative operations, including tasks related to monitoring and evaluation, cannot be considered.”

At the same time, individual government representatives expressed that they are open to proposals to enhance their capacities in this area. One important aspect in enhancing evaluation practices would be to develop public sector officials' understandings of what can be achieved through M&E, as it is frequently seen through the more limited lens of “control” (Stolyarenko et al., 2012). In an interview, a member of civil society highlighted: “The development of an effective monitoring and evaluation system requires the establishment of an appropriate culture, along with a shared understanding of the importance of transparency at all levels. It is essential to recognise that M&E is not so much about control, but rather about improvement and the ability to view one's own work from an external perspective.” Awareness of the terminology is more enhanced among development partners and organisations implementing international funds (Stolyarenko et al., 2012).

3.2.3.2 M&E in Line Ministries

The current approach to M&E across the different line ministries remains largely sectoral and fragmented, with individual departments conducting monitoring activities within their specific areas of responsibility. M&E-related tasks are often delegated to internal audit and records management departments, which are primarily concerned with compliance, control and financial accountability, rather than with learning or evidence-based policy improvement. Stakeholder interviews confirmed the lack of dedicated M&E units across ministries.

Internal capacities for conducting evaluations vary among different line ministries but generally remain insufficient. While some ministries – for example, the Ministry of Education and Science, the Ministry of Economy, the Ministry of Environmental Protection and the Ministry of Health – are not mandated with M&E of state policies and programmes, regulations for other ministries, in contrast, include (mostly limited) provisions for such functions. The Ministry for Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine and the Ministry of Digital Transformation are considered the two most advanced ministries in using M&E practices. These two examples are presented in more detail below. However, almost all ministries are involved in formulating, implementing and monitoring the effectiveness of the state sanctions policy within their areas of competence.

Ministry for Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine

The Ukrainian government's most notable example in terms of explicitly defined M&E functions is the Ministry for Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine, which is responsible for, among other things (CMU, 2022):

- M&E of the implementation of state regional policies
- Monitoring of the socio-economic development of regions and communities
- M&E of the implementation of the State Strategy for Regional Development of Ukraine, its Action Plan, and regional development programmes and projects (CMU, 2020a)
- Establishing and managing a unified M&E geoinformation system to develop regions and territorial communities

These functions are handled by the Department for the Implementation of Priority Regional Development and Critical Infrastructure Projects, the Department of Investment Policy, and the Department of Strategic Planning and Regional Policy.

Although local governments have gained more autonomy through decentralization, central authorities, particularly the Ministry of Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine, continue to oversee and guide the activities of local governments (CMU, 2014a). This ensures that local policies align with national standards and provides technical support for local implementation. The Ministry of Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine also plays a key role in monitoring the decentralization reform and related changes. However, formal evaluations of local policies are often ad hoc, with evaluations typically linked to broader national and local development programmes or specific policy cycles rather than regular, annual assessments.

Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine

In the Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine, some monitoring activities are managed by the Directorate for Strategic Planning, including the monitoring of International Technical Assistance (ITA) projects involving this Ministry. Additionally, the Department of Systematic Development of Administrative

Services includes a unit responsible for monitoring the quality of services, actively leveraging user feedback from the Diia portal and other e-services.²⁹

This Ministry actively fosters a culture of project management, where monitoring is a key component. According to representatives from the Ministry, project management tools – including M&E – are instrumental in achieving high performance and maintaining Ukraine’s leading positions in international digitalization rankings. The Ministry has paid significant attention to evaluating the impact of open data in Ukraine, for instance within the framework of the project “Transparency and Accountability in Public-Administration and Services”, which was funded by the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) (Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine, 2022). The Ministry of Digital Transformation is a beneficiary of numerous ITA projects, which provide funding and support for evaluating the outcomes of its activities.

Further Line Ministries

Other ministries that implement M&E functions to some extent are listed here:

- **The Ministry of Energy of Ukraine** has no department directly responsible for M&E in a broad sense. The Directorate for Strategic Planning and European Integration ensures preliminary assessment of legislative acts in this specific area. This Ministry is involved in appraising and selecting investment projects and environmentally focused initiatives in renewable energy and alternative gas fuels, as well as monitoring their implementation.
- **The Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine** monitors (but does not evaluate) the development and implementation of state investment projects and state support for investment activities.
- **Ministry of National Unity of Ukraine** (until December 2024 “Ministry for Reintegration of the Temporarily Occupied Territories of Ukraine”) monitors the impact of Russia’s armed aggression and temporary occupation on the socio-economic development of the state and some economic sectors. This Ministry also co-ordinates recovery and peacebuilding measures and monitors their implementation.
- **The Ministry of Finance of Ukraine** is involved in tasks related to European integration, particularly improving policy development procedures. According to a representative, M&E is considered within this context, because one of this Ministry’s key areas of work is supporting European integration. A significant portion of the Ministry of Finance’s responsibilities include monitoring budget programmes, monitoring and verifying budget payments, and overseeing the use of loan funds received from international partners. This Ministry is responsible for monitoring the implementation of the Reforms Matrix as described in section 3.2.2 (CMU, 2025).
- **The Ministry of Environmental Protection and Natural Resources** contains the Department of Ecological Assessment, which is explicitly devoted to M&E in relation to its respective state policy.

3.2.3.3 *The Parliament’s Role in Monitoring and Oversight*³⁰

The VRU shares legislative initiative with the Ukrainian government. In practice, over 80% of draft legislation is initiated by the VRU (EC, 2023). Nevertheless, the institution’s legislative capacities, particularly in terms of procedural and methodological tools for conducting “impact assessment of draft legislation and ex post legislative evaluation”, need to be strengthened (EC, 2024a) – notably, legislative drafts submitted by parliamentarians “often lack proper explanatory notes and/or impact assessments, which affects the quality of laws” (EC, 2023). Although the parliament formally oversees the implementation of public policy, no systematic monitoring practices or dedicated evaluation systems exist within the VRU. However, the

29 The Ministry of Digital Transformation uses the Diia portal for e-identification and user authentication (Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine, n.d.a).

30 This section was prepared in co-operation with Dr Denys Zhernovyi, Deputy Head of Parliamentary Faction Secretariat.

establishment of the Parliamentary Research Service in August 2022 is a step towards strengthening the VRU's ability to integrate evidence and analysis into its legislative processes.

Despite the war, the VRU has continued to fulfil its legislative functions, with a focus on defence, security and EU integration (EC, 2023). The war has negatively affected parliamentary oversight mechanisms and transparency, with parliamentary activities currently "mostly limited to closed meetings between leaders of majority or parliamentary groups and individual ministers" (EC, 2024a: 23). Furthermore, journalists are not authorised to attend plenary and other meetings. It will be crucial to remove these limitations in public policy and consultation mechanisms once martial law has been lifted (EC, 2023).

In line with other EU member state models, parliamentary accountability mechanisms include the "approval process of the government's political programme, annual reporting, regular Q&A sessions, MP's requests" (EC, 2023: 18). According to Article 11 of the "Law on Committees of the VRU", parliamentary committees perform a control oversight function. At the time of writing, 23 committees are responsible for legislative oversight (EC, 2023). These committees face a complex task: balancing the development of state policy with proper monitoring of its implementation as outlined in the original plan. In monitoring the government's execution of long-term policies, committees may request for relevant government reports to be submitted and analysed. To supplement these reports and provide additional context, committees can invite appropriate ministers to meetings and request necessary explanations. This direct interaction allows committees to understand government performance better.

The most common forms of parliamentary oversight occur during plenary sessions. These include tracking the performance of the CMU Programme of Activity, holding the government question hour, and reviewing information and reports. Parliamentary hearings are another important form of holding the government accountable; after these hearings, resolutions are adopted to approve recommendations.

The effectiveness of parliamentary oversight over public policy implementation across various sectors largely depends on the clarity of the government's commitments: when the government sets clear and measurable goals, parliamentary oversight and monitoring becomes more effective. In Ukraine, these obligations are outlined in the CMU's Programme of Activity, "performance indicators for evaluating government actions. In the event of non-fulfilment, the possibility of political sanctions is opened.

The government question hour is a critical tool of parliamentary oversight, as defined by Article 35 of the "Law on the CMU". This procedure allows members of the parliament to engage directly with government representatives, including ministers and senior officials, fostering real-time accountability on policy decisions, legislative initiatives and pressing national issues. During the question hour, members of the parliament can ask questions on matters of public interest, including the implementation of laws, execution of government programmes and responses to emerging challenges. This interaction not only promotes transparency but also provides the government with an opportunity to clarify its actions and justify its decisions in a formal, public setting.

During the IX convocation of the VRU, the government question hour was held over 50 times. However, its regularity was modified with the introduction of martial law in 2022 and corresponding changes in the parliamentary schedule. Since the beginning of 2024, the question hour has been held more regularly again, with a primary focus on defence capability, energy security, financial stability and European integration. In this context, limited time allocation, quality of responses and political manoeuvring all undermine its impact. Strengthening the question hour's procedural framework and ensuring timely, substantive responses would enhance its role as a cornerstone of democratic governance in Ukraine.

Listening to information and reports is another vital aspect of parliamentary oversight. Under the Constitution of Ukraine, such information should be presented as part of the government's performance monitoring. The VRU, for example, hears reports on the progress of the CMU's Programme of Activity, the activities of temporary investigative and special commissions, updates from cabinet members, and reports on topics determined by parliamentary hearings.

3.2.3.4 The Role of Civil Society Organisations in M&E

Ukraine's legal framework supports civil society participation in governance. The Constitution and various laws, including the Law "On Access to Public Information", guarantee citizens' and CSOs' rights to engage in decision making, planning, budgeting and monitoring processes. In 2024, the VRU adopted a new law on lobbying that regulates policy change (VRU, 2024a): it includes expanded access to decision-making forums and more systematic engagement in reform processes, as reflected in recent civil society development strategies. Strategic documents that promote CSO engagement include the National Strategy for Civil Society Development in Ukraine for 2021-2026 (CMU, 2021a) and its related Action Plan for 2024 (CMU, 2023b), the National Strategy for Creating a Barrier-Free Environment, and the National Human Rights Strategy (EC, 2023; Krasnenko, 2025; Mrak and Zuber, 2023). Further, the government plans to integrate CSO representatives in EU acquis negotiations. M&E of public policy through involvement in public councils remains insufficient (Krasnenko, 2025). Common forms of public participation include public consultations, hearings, councils and monitoring activities (CMU, 2010). However, the practical implementation of these provisions often lacks clarity and consistency, their engagement is limited, and CSOs initiate the M&E of projects or policies themselves (CMU, 2010).

Developments since Russia's Full-Scale Invasion in 2022

Russia's full-scale invasion posed challenges to CSOs' engagement with the government. Martial law has imposed additional restrictions on public engagement (President of Ukraine, 2022 February 24), meaning government officials have reduced their engagement with the public. At national and regional level, collaboration continues only with long-standing CSO partners (USAID et al., 2020). Furthermore, restrictions have been placed on advocacy, freedom of assembly and public information (USAID et al., 2023a). As noted by a representative of the Secretariat of the CMU, interaction with the public is currently limited (for example, access to the Secretariat building is restricted), significantly fewer meetings are being held, and some consultative and advisory bodies have either been disbanded or are no longer active (such as the Council on Entrepreneurship).

CSOs are involved in implementing humanitarian, recovery and development initiatives of various scale and focus, often funded by development partners but also supported through crowdfunding, donations, member fees or social businesses. They are both beneficiaries and implementers of M&E capacity development programmes, integrating evaluation into their operations to improve the effectiveness of their projects. CSOs rely heavily on funding from development partners to carry out their activities, highlighting both the capacity present in civil society and the challenges of ensuring sustainability without external support (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024; EU, n.d.).

Public Consultations and Councils

Although public consultations are conducted across government bodies, their effectiveness is limited because of the lack of adequate mechanisms for interaction between public authorities and CSOs (CEDEM, 2023a). Legislation does not clearly define who can initiate public hearings or the specific issues requiring such hearings, making it challenging for CSOs to influence policy effectively. Public councils, which are intended as advisory bodies that comprise various civil society representatives, often function in a declarative manner without substantial influence on policy making.

Proposals resulting from public hearings must be considered by local government bodies. However, legislation does not define who has the right to initiate public hearings or participate in them, nor does it specify the issues for which public hearings are mandatory. This lack of clarity makes public hearings a challenging tool for CSOs to use in influencing state policy.

Public councils are established under government agencies to promote public participation in developing and implementing state and regional policies (CMU, 2010). Legislation defines a public council as "a temporary advisory and consultative body established to promote public participation in the formation and implementation of state policy. The council may include representatives of CSOs, religious and charitable organisations, creative unions, professional associations, employers' organisations, non-governmental

media, and other civil society institutions” (CMU, 2019) with an expertise in the relevant field. Public councils allow citizens to scrutinise and directly influence policy making – if their activities were not merely declarative in nature, which is often the case (Transparency International Ukraine, 2021).

Role of Civil Society in Monitoring Public Policy and Government Activities

CSOs are involved in monitoring public policies. Development partners often support public monitoring as a key function of civil society that is problem-focused and tightly linked to oversight activities. Civil society platforms, such as the Ukrainian National Platform of the Eastern Partnership Civil Society Forum and the EU-Ukraine Civil Society Platform, also play a vital role in monitoring government actions, tracking policy implementation and holding officials accountable. For example, representatives of Working Group 3 (Environment, Climate Change, and Energy Security) of the Ukrainian National Platform of the Eastern Partnership Civil Society Forum conducted studies on the implementation of the European Commission’s recommendations under Chapter 27, “Environment and Climate Change” (EPL, 2024). Moreover, civil society has established a coalition of Ukrainian and international organisations working for Ukraine’s Reconstruction Integrity, Sustainability and Efficiency (RISE) that aim to monitor reconstruction spending (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024).

Civil Society Organisations’ Involvement in Public Evaluation

In Ukraine, civil society’s involvement in government evaluations remains limited, primarily due to the system’s internal limitations, which hinder how much non-governmental actors can systematically contribute to government-led evaluations – particularly at the policy level. The results of the survey conducted in the framework of this analysis show that only a limited number of CSOs consider themselves involved in evaluating public policies (Figure 5). Over the past decade, public engagement has been actively incorporated into the creation of policy documents supported by different development partners, including the EU FORBIZ project (EU4Business, 2021), USAID ERA (USAID, 2023) and Regional Development Strategies supported by UNDP (see Luhansk Regional State Administration (Working Groups) and Regional Military-Civil Administration, 2016).

Figure 5 Survey Results: Involvement of Ukrainian CSOs in Evaluating Public Policy

Is your CSO involved in evaluating public policy?

Source: DEval, own illustration, based on the survey conducted as part of the case study (n=50).

In general, Ukrainian CSOs are not expected to be active in delivery evaluations; they are more experienced in monitoring public policy. CSOs and the media have access to evaluations that could be used as tools for transparency, accountability and policy advocacy, yet these are rarely utilised. CSOs utilise available evaluation results – particularly those from international projects – to advocate for policy changes, channel demands to public institutions, influence public policy and hold the government accountable to the public. However, the absence of a national framework or legislative support for civil society's role in evaluation creates significant challenges in consistently translating evaluation findings into actionable policy recommendations. As the analysis showed, the public policy evaluations carried out by the development partners are often publicly inaccessible – with some exceptions, such as those by the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ) and the International Labour Organization (ILO). However, based on the experience of UEA members, development partners share their evaluation results with respective policy makers, although monitoring of the implementation of recommendations from those evaluations is limited.

Although civil society representatives are not satisfied with the level of their engagement (see Figure 6 below), some positive examples of their monitoring are described in Box 3 below. Civil society representatives actively participate in evaluations conducted within international projects, often as individual experts. These projects invite CSOs to join evaluation activities, thereby providing a temporary platform for engagement. Through such collaborations, CSOs contribute valuable insights and sectoral expertise – but this participation is largely project-specific and lacks continuity at the national level.

Figure 6 Survey Results: NGOs' Satisfaction with their Engagement in Evaluating Public Policies

Source: DEval, own illustration, based on the survey conducted as part of the case study (n=50).

Note: The bars show the proportion of individuals who selected the respective number.

Some CSOs implement advocacy projects, providing recommendations for improving existing regulatory documents and programmes. They also monitor the implementation of territorial community development strategies, regional target programmes and regional development strategies. However, despite their specialised monitoring efforts, none of these organisations provide a comprehensive policy evaluation service. Furthermore, limited access to information has made it more challenging for CSOs to carry out monitoring activities. They obtain information using publicly available sources and formal requests, including state and local authority websites, but due to martial law these systems are currently out of operation, leading to a lack of information and delayed responses (Krasnenko, 2025).

Box 3 Examples of CSO Involvement in M&E of Public Policies

The **Institute for Economic Research and Policy Consulting (IER)** systematically evaluates various aspects of customs operations (IER, 2021, 2023). Materials developed by the IER have been used by the State Customs Service of Ukraine and published on its website (State Customs Service of Ukraine, n.d.).

The **Institute of Analysis and Advocacy** conducts research on the activities of the Accounting Chamber (Vavreniuk et al., 2021) and provides recommendations (Institute of Analytics and Advocacy, 2024a). Additionally, the organisation's experts explore potential ways to finance communities for infrastructure recovery (Institute of Analytics and Advocacy, 2024b). Recommendations outlined in its analytical reports have been adopted by stakeholders.

Ecoaction monitors environmental policies. It has provided recommendations regarding the Draft Law "On the Principles of State Climate Policy" (Ecoaction, 2024a) and the Ukraine Plan (Ecoaction, 2024b), and has commented on the National Energy and Climate Plan of Ukraine (Ecoaction, 2024c). The organisation has also initiated the development of a consolidated civil society position on the just transition of Ukraine's coal regions (Ecoaction, 2024d).

The **Centre for Democracy and Rule of Law** is an analytic and advocacy centre that monitors legislation and national and international practices in the fields of media, access to public information and public health, including monitoring regulatory legal acts in television and radio broadcasting concerning adoption of the Law of Ukraine "On Media" (CEDEM, 2023b) and overseeing the implementation of the Law of Ukraine "On Access to Public Information" (CEDEM, 2025). The organisation also provides legal opinions.

Transparency International Ukraine focuses on anti-corruption measures and monitors the efficiency and transparency of the Ukrainian public procurement system, including supporting developments such as managing the creation of the Prozorro electronic public procurement system. After transferring it to the state-owned enterprise Prozorro, the organisation concentrated on monitoring compliance with the law and on developing analytical tools (Transparency International Ukraine, n.d.).

The **DEJURE Foundation** continuously analyses and monitors justice sector reforms, actively overseeing judges' integrity based on their records and tracking legal developments related to the judiciary in Ukraine. In 2024, the organisation conducted an assessment of judges, reviewing the effectiveness of the qualification process with the participation of new members of the High Qualification Commission of Judges and the High Council of Justice (Zelinskyi et al., 2024). DEJURE also outlines the conditions necessary for successfully cleansing the judiciary.

DiXi Group focuses on energy policy monitoring, providing regular analysis of developments in Ukraine's energy sector. Since the start of Russia's full-scale invasion, the organisation has been publishing weekly analytics and monitoring reports on energy policies and sectoral developments (DiXi Group, 2025a, n.d.a). Additionally, DiXi Group conducts monthly monitoring of permitting activities and regulatory changes in the extractive industries, along with other key topics (DiXi Group, 2025b).

Internal M&E of Civil Society Organisations' Activities

CSOs, which are among the primary implementers of numerous humanitarian and recovery projects, are required to demonstrate the effectiveness of their programmes and ensure efficient use of resources, particularly in the context of increased international support, post-war recovery efforts, and the increasing need for accountability, transparency and evidence-informed decision making. This makes M&E capacity development crucially important for CSOs.

Government Use of Civil Sector Evaluations

The government makes efforts to consider M&E results produced by the civil sector. Among the 11 CSO respondents to our survey who were involved in evaluating state policy, only two indicated that their results were ignored by the government or parliament. The remaining respondents reported that their

recommendations were either wholly or partially taken into consideration. This is a positive development, though other studies provide a more cautious assessment of the government's readiness to adopt civil sector recommendations (CEDEM, 2023a).

3.2.3.5 *The Role of Other Stakeholders in M&E of Public Policies*

In addition to state actors and CSOs, other key stakeholders also contribute to the national evaluation system.

Consulting and auditing firms: international consulting and auditing firms often implement technical assistance projects funded by development partners at national and regional level, adhere closely to international evaluation standards, and promote principles such as “Do No Harm”. By integrating national and international expertise, they contribute significantly to Ukraine's evaluation system.

Domestic Ukrainian consulting firms, by contrast, are primarily oriented towards marketing and sociological research. Although these firms are proficient in survey methodologies and data collection, they often lack the expertise required for comprehensive M&E aligned with international standards.

Sociological and marketing research firms (for example, GfK Ukraine, 4Service and many others): these companies conduct public opinion surveys, market research and sociological assessments that may inform policy. However, they generally lack formal M&E expertise.

Academic institutions and universities (for example Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Kyiv School of Economics and others): despite being involved in applied research and collaborating on evaluation with public institutions, public universities are often hampered by underfunding and the migration of experienced researchers to the private sector, which affects the quality and consistency of evaluation outputs.

Independent consultants and evaluation experts: these professionals deliver evaluations of projects and programmes, contribute to larger evaluations through consortia, and often build the link to local expertise and context understanding. The growing international assistance to Ukraine has led to increased demand for local evaluators, opening a new professional field. At the same time, available training opportunities for evaluators have not increased, leading to a mismatch in evaluation expertise and demand. Professional expertise in monitoring project and programme developments has been sufficiently developed through development aid. Independent evaluators might organise themselves in the UEA, which is further described next.

Role of VOPEs: the UEA is the only officially registered VOPE in Ukraine. Founded in 2011 as an informal group of evaluation-enthusiastic professionals, it was institutionalised in 2013. As of late 2024, the UEA comprises over 60 evaluation professionals, the majority of whom are women (45), working across sectors as independent consultants or within organisations (also see Box 4). Although the UEA represents only a small fraction of the evaluators active in Ukraine, the association plays a co-ordinating role in the profession. To join the UEA, the requirements include familiarization with the UEA by-law, a membership application form and an online questionnaire. The constituent board decides on new members. The annual membership fee is set at 600 Ukrainian hryvnias (approximately 15 euros) in 2025; this builds the financial basis of the association. However, the membership fees alone do not cover all expenses, and additional funding would be required to ensure sustainability or make organisational developments such as establishing a secretariat. According to its statute, the UEA cannot conduct evaluation assignments to avoid competition – and therefore a conflict of interest – with its members.

The UEA's activities targeting a wider expert audience include, among others:

- Publishing the first Ukrainian-language M&E glossary (Goroshko et al., 2016)
- Promoting the formal recognition of the evaluator profession, which is currently not regulated in the Ukraine's official list of economic activities³¹
- Advocating for national evaluation policy, including establishing minimum qualification requirements for evaluators and providing information material and publications on evaluation standards, such as a brochure published in 2016 (UEA 2016)
- Offering limited training and certification programmes, often dependent on external funding by development partners
- Providing networking opportunities for evaluators
- Developing a dispute resolution and quality assurance mechanism, similar to those used by self-regulatory organisations
- Collaborating with academic institutions, NGOs and international partners

One example of the UEA's activities is its July 2024 open letter to Denys Shmyhal, the Prime Minister of Ukraine at that time, and Olena Shuliak, the Chair of the Parliamentary Committee on State Building, Local Governance, Regional Development and Urban Planning. In the letter, the UEA asked for a national evaluation infrastructure to be developed to support EU integration goals. At the time of writing, no official response has been received.

Since Russia's full-scale invasion, the UEA has increased its capacity in humanitarian evaluations and actively shares its expertise with its partners and international colleagues. Its partnerships and networks include the European Evaluation Society (EES),³² the Active Learning Network for Accountability and Performance in Humanitarian Action (ALNAP), and the Institute for Evaluations and Social Analyses (INESAN) in the Czech Republic. Furthermore, the UEA actively collaborates with national universities (such as the Faculty of Sociology of the Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv and Borys Grinchenko Kyiv Metropolitan University), the wider academic community (for example, the Institute for Economics and Forecasting and the Institute of Sociology) and CSOs. In 2024, a UEA member participated as an instructor in the "International Program for Development Evaluation Training" (IPDET), the world-renowned international training programme in evaluation.

31 In the Ukrainian context, including a profession in the list of economic activities is important for several reasons: it means that legal entities, entrepreneurs and self-employed people may clearly indicate their profession; it creates better opportunities for the development of the profession; and it establishes (minimal) qualification requirements.

32 The UEA sought free or discounted institutional membership, but this request was denied, making full participation financially unfeasible. At present, the UEA does not receive funding from EES or other organisations, such as foundations, to support its institutional engagement.

Box 4 Example: Co-operation between the Government of Ukraine and the UEA to Enhance Evaluation in Decentralisation

Experts from the UEA sometimes collaborate with the government on analysing drafted documents. For instance, during the implementation of the “Strengthening Decentralisation in Ukraine” project (2017-2018), they prepared and published expert evaluations of M&E systems for several national strategies and programmes:

- “Concept of the Reform of Local Self-Government and Territorial Organisation of Power in Ukraine”
- State Targeted Social Programme on Combating Human Trafficking
- State Social-Economic Program of Construction (Purchase) of Affordable Housing for 2010-2017
- State Target Social Program ‘Youth of Ukraine’ for 2016-2020
- National Strategy for Promoting Civil Society Development in Ukraine for 2016-2020
- M&E of the activities of Ukrainian authorities

This is a notable example of a VOPE’s involvement in evaluating state policy. However, it was driven by international development partners rather than supported by the government. It also lacked a systematic approach, being limited to the development of expert conclusions rather than a comprehensive evaluation.

Media: investigative journalism plays an important role in overseeing policy actions and project implementations. In Ukraine, investigative journalism primarily focuses on major corruption cases, involving politicians, government and parliament members, and public funds.

Between November 2023 and August 2024, public procurement and the use of budget funds were the most popular topic of journalistic investigations, with 20% of all materials included in Regional Press Development Institute research focused on this issue. Almost as many investigative texts (19%) related to the topic of war – Russian aggression, war crimes, collaborationism and propaganda. Abuse of power, corruption and illegal enrichment accounted for 18% of investigations. Other journalistic investigations looked at business with the occupiers (13%), property declarations by high-ranking officials (4%), corruption during reconstruction (4%), land fraud (3%), mobilization and illegal departures abroad (3%), and other topics (16%) (Detector Media, 2024).

The main challenge in Ukraine is how to effectively utilise the results of such investigations, because the law enforcement and juridical systems are not efficient enough. Overall, although media plays an important role in overseeing state policy, its role regarding evidence-informed policy making remains limited.

3.2.4 Availability and Quality of Statistical and Administrative Data

Ukraine’s national data system is aligned with the EU’s statistical office and is relatively well developed, ensuring open access to statistical and administrative data on the country. Although the available data is reliable, it is not fully comprehensive – key weaknesses include a lack of disaggregation and unsuitability of the data for tracking long-term trends. Due to the imposition of martial law and ongoing security concerns, the war has adversely affected data availability and reliability. To address the data requirements for a just and effective recovery and reconstruction of Ukraine, governmental and international platforms are monitoring war-related damages and needs, with support from the international community.

Public Statistical and Government Data

M&E is dependent on the availability of good and reliable data (GEI, 2022). In Ukraine, the State Statistics Service (Ukrstat), an official government body, is responsible for collecting, analysing and disseminating official data (CMU, 2014b). Ukraine’s official statistical system has been harmonised with Eurostat, the statistical office of the EU, for over 15 years. Overall, a wide range of data is available. However, despite Ukrstat’s adoption of European methodological standards, government authorities’ specific data needs

for informed decision making are not fully met. This is particularly evident in Ukrstat's selection of statistical data, where data collection remains optional under EU regulations, and in its insufficient disaggregation of data. Furthermore, periodic changes in data collection methodologies disrupt time series, creating challenges for long-term analysis.

The decentralisation reform in Ukraine, ongoing since 2014, is not sufficiently reflected in the official statistics system. Most data is still only available at the regional (oblast) level rather than at the community level, which significantly limits the ability of local communities to monitor and evaluate local development. However, in 2024, the government adopted the Decentralisation Roadmap, which provided the impetus for the Ministry for Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine – together with USAID HOVERLA, the Ministry of Digital Transformation and Ukrstat – to create a geographic information system (GIS) for regional development (CMU, 2024c).

As indicated by its annual user satisfaction index (Ukrstat, 2023), Ukrstat's data does not fully meet user needs. In 2023, only 38% of respondents reported that the data fully satisfied their needs, while just 21% expressed complete satisfaction with its timeliness and reliability.

Ukraine's open data system is a significant source of statistics and government data. The country has made considerable progress in advancing its open data landscape through the official portal – data.gov.ua (Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine, n.d.b) – which provides a comprehensive array of data on government spending, public services and economic indicators to strengthen transparency. Various ministries and government agencies are responsible for collecting and publishing data and reports within their respective sectors, such as education (Government of Ukraine, n.d.a), health (Government of Ukraine, n.d.b) and agriculture (Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine, 2024).

In addition, some non-state actors have developed specific dashboards on various issues, such as Energy Map (DiXi Group, n.d.b), which provides energy statistics.

Use of Data

These openly accessible data sets are increasingly used by researchers, policy makers and CSOs to monitor government performance and assess public policies, thereby enhancing transparency and accountability. The value of using data for policy making was highlighted in a revised law in the field of statistics in 2022, which identifies the timely provision of impartial and objective official state statistical information as the primary goal of state statistical activities³³ (VRU, 2022a). This revision of the goals for the functioning of state statistics – explicitly including policy making as one of the key uses of official statistical data – can mark a legislative shift in the role of statistics in governance.

Implications of the Full-Scale Invasion

The war has posed challenges in terms of transparency and use of official data. Martial law and security concerns have necessitated temporary restrictions on certain data sets, causing publicly available data to be fragmented. However, efforts are under way to safely restore access to critical data that supports anti-corruption measures and guides post-war reconstruction planning (BRDO, 2024; EU, 2022).

Furthermore, the Law “On the Protection of the Interests of Reporting Entities and Other Documents During Martial Law or a State of War” (VRU, 2022b) permits entities that do not receive budgetary funds to suspend their reporting obligations during the period of martial law due to war-related disruptions, damages or

³³ This information is essential for informing the public, formulating and monitoring economic and social policies, and enabling state authorities to make well-founded decisions based on the results of state statistical observations. These efforts aim to ensure sustainable development, economic well-being, human rights and compliance with Ukraine's commitments under existing international agreements, as well as to support scientific research.

destructions of companies. Consequently, this has led to delays in data publication, and data quality has declined because not all entities are submitting reports. Household surveys have also encountered difficulties; the most recent available data comes from 2022. These factors are limiting the transparency of government's actions.

As a consequence of the war, user satisfaction and trust in Ukraine's official statistics have further declined, as the annual user satisfaction index by Ukrstat shows: confidence in official statistics dropped from 65% in 2021 to 52% in 2023. However, Ukrstat's digital transformation should improve the timeliness of statistical data and thereby enhance its usefulness for evaluations (CMU, 2023c).

The high intensity of the war poses challenges to the credibility of publicly available data, particularly in light of significant disinformation and misinformation. The war has also affected accuracy of information, the ability to verify it, and the recording of specific data, because field verification may not be possible (Heidelberg Institute for International Conflict Research, 2023; World Bank et al., 2025).

Data in light of Recovery and Reconstruction: War Damages and Needs

In addition to international efforts to collect data on the implications of the war, the Ukrainian government and CSOs – with support from international partners – are currently implementing several initiatives to collect, record and analyse information on infrastructure damage and the needs of vulnerable populations caused by Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine. The most comprehensive of these efforts are the Rapid Damage and Needs Assessments (RDNA), jointly conducted by the World Bank, the Government of Ukraine, the European Commission, the United Nations and other partners. These assessments take stock of the physical, financial and social impacts of the invasion. Various independent initiatives also exist, such as "Eyes on Russia", launched by the Centre for Information Resilience, which collects and verifies data on the war's effects (C4ADS innovation for peace, n.d.).

A key platform that is transparently collecting and organizing data on war damages and reconstruction needs is the Digital Restoration Ecosystem for Accountable Management (DREAM), established by the Ukrainian government with support from development partners. Additionally, various state and non-state initiatives are collecting and publishing data, such as the Register of Damaged and Destroyed Property or the "Analytical platform for the recovery of cities and communities", run by Restart Ukraine and UNDP. There are also non-state initiatives like Big Recovery Portal, a component of "The Recovery Spending Watchdog", which monitors national budget expenditures and external funds by development partners (Centre for Economic Strategy et al., n.d.). For an overview of key platforms, see Annex 7.2.

Analysis of these platforms shows that the Ukrainian government primarily collects technical information about damaged objects, the estimated cost of their restoration and the amounts of compensation provided to people for repairs. At the same time, the share of damaged or destroyed objects recorded in the registries is significantly lower than 100%. The share has been gradually improving, with current levels approaching 60 to 70%. Discrepancies in the data on the education sector illustrate this: according to government data, over 3,790 educational institutions have been damaged or destroyed since the invasion began. However, as of 10 March 2025, the DREAM platform contains information on only 2,611 active projects in the education sector, while 1,435 projects are in the initiation stage (Government of Ukraine, 2025). Similar situations can be observed in healthcare and other sectors. This shows that the country's actual needs for recovery projects are much greater and require the collection of more detailed and higher-quality information with a proper level of data reliability and disaggregation.

A comprehensive database is crucial to strategically prioritise and sequence recovery and reconstruction efforts. The absence of data on war-related damages poses risks to ensuring inclusivity and upholding the United Nations principle to "Leave No One Behind". Furthermore, reliable data is essential for adhering to the principle to "Do No Harm", because inadequate consideration of specific communities may result in tensions or disparities. Although some sociological studies supported by development partners do focus on the challenges faced by specific vulnerable populations and businesses, these studies do not track changes over time or are limited to a narrow range of territories.

3.2.5 Capacity Development Initiatives and Training Relevant to M&E

Long-term capacity development programmes remain scarce in Ukraine. Existing short-term training initiatives are often fragmented and lack a systematic approach, resulting in incomplete coverage of essential topics – particularly in areas such as advanced data analysis and sector-specific evaluation methods. The absence of a formal, recognised certification system for M&E professionals in Ukraine has created inconsistencies in training quality and professional standards. The growing demand for highly professional evaluation services from development partners, driven by increased international assistance due to the war, suggests that the existing training provisions and limited number of M&E professionals may not be sufficient to meet international evaluation needs.

On the “supply side” of evaluations, skilled professionals, capable institutions and appropriate tools are needed to ensure quality evaluations. This entails continuous training, professional networks, context-sensitive methods and capacity development for different actor groups.

As part of this discussion paper, available M&E capacity development initiatives in Ukraine were examined at four levels:

- Higher education programmes preparing young professionals for careers in M&E or related fields
- Professional certification programmes focusing on the practical and strategic application of M&E skills for mid-career and senior professionals
- Executive or leadership-level training programmes focusing on practical and strategic applications for mid-career and senior professionals
- Workshops and short-term training addressing immediate, practical M&E needs

While the research conducted shows that Ukraine has programmes available across all four categories of M&E training, gaps remain, leaving important areas insufficiently addressed. For more detailed information on capacity development in M&E, see Annex 7.3.

At the level of higher education, the only master's degree-level programme in Ukraine that directly focuses on M&E is the M&E of Social Programmes, with concentration on the management of social projects and programmes, offered by Borys Grinchenko Kyiv Metropolitan University. Some other attempts have been made to launch master's degree-level programmes on M&E, but they were not popular among prospective students and were abandoned. Although emerging evaluators are included in evaluation teams, evaluation is rather rarely considered as a career path.

Some courses on M&E are delivered as part of master's degree-level and bachelor's degree-level programmes in other Ukrainian universities, for example:³⁴

- Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Faculty of Sociology: Technologies of Evaluation Research and Evaluation of Social Programmes and Projects, both courses for bachelor's students
- Sumy State University, Academic and Research Institute of Business, Economics and Management: Monitoring and Evaluation of Management Activities course (Mishenina and Kobushko, 2022)
- Uzhhorod National University, Faculty of Health and Physical Education: Monitoring and Evaluation in the System of Public Health, a course for master's students
- University of Customs and Finance, module “Monitoring, Evaluation, Scientific Research: What? When? How?” within the discipline Methodology of Scientific Research and Management of Scientific Projects for postgraduate students; module “Monitoring and Evaluation of Processes in the Public Sphere” for master's students

³⁴ The list is not exhaustive because many other universities offer such courses as part of their curricula.

Various certification programmes exist, some of which are implemented as part of initiatives funded by development partners. However, such programmes remain relatively rare overall. For instance, in 2023, the Institute of Leadership and Management of the Ukrainian Catholic University offered a one-time certification programme “Monitoring and Evaluation of Decisions and Projects for the Recovery and Development of Ukrainian Communities During the War and Post-War Period”. The programme was delivered under the project “Strengthening democratic resilience through civic participation during the war and in the post-war context in Ukraine” implemented by the Council of Europe and may not be repeated once the project is over.

Brief executive, leadership and professional development programmes are offered by the National Agency of Ukraine on Civil Service (NAUCS) as part of its professional development programme for public servants. The courses, which are developed both by the NAUCS and by universities, includes the following:

- Methods of Evaluating Projects Implemented with Budgetary Funds (delivered at various locations, including Zhytomyr Regional Centre of Professional Development and Chernivtsi Regional Centre of Professional Development)
- M&E of Programmes and Projects (Zaporizhzhia Regional Centre of Professional Development)
- Analysis of Statistical, Sociological, and Spatial Data, and Big Data Analytics for the Evaluation and Monitoring of Regional Development (Kirovohrad Regional Centre of Professional Development)
- Needs Assessment in the Development of Public Policies and Planning for National Recovery (Higher School of Public Administration, Ukrainian School of Governance)

No similar courses are available for other audiences.

An area closely related to M&E capacity development is policy analysis and policy evaluation. The crucial difference is that while policy analysis deals with pending or future decisions, policy evaluation focuses on a policy or programme that is already in place.

Workshops and short-term training courses are typically provided by CSOs through internationally funded projects, often free of charge, as well as by individual M&E experts on a fee basis (see Box 5 for an example). These are predominantly available for beginners, while executive-level and certification programmes remain scarce or difficult to access. Most university programmes offer an overview of conventional data collection methods, both quantitative and qualitative, but do not cover more specialised M&E topics such as participatory approaches, rapid assessments or outcome mapping.

Ukrainian CSOs actively work on M&E-related manuals, most of which provide an introductory-level overview of topics such as why the M&E system is needed, an introduction to results-based management, methods of data collection (including interviews, focus groups and surveys), the development of final reports and dissemination of information. These manuals often also cover topics specific to the intended audience (such as M&E in HIV/AIDS prevention (Alliance for Public Health, 2018), regional policy analysis, education) and Ukrainian legislation relevant to implementing M&E in those areas (such as decrees of the CMU regulating M&E of state regional policies, or an M&E system of measures aimed at preventing the spread of the HIV epidemic).

Box 5 Example: East Europe Foundation

East Europe Foundation is a Ukrainian NGO that implements technical and humanitarian assistance projects funded by development partners. While East Europe Foundation develops its own M&E systems, it also supports its sub-grantees, other NGOs, in developing robust M&E capacities. As part of these efforts, it has developed a free distance-learning course on M&E for NGOs (EEF, 2023), in co-operation with the UEA and with financial support from the EU. The course introduces NGO representatives to the main M&E concepts and principles and includes video lectures and tests for self-control (EEF, 2023).

While international partners occasionally support national evaluation capacities, no institutional or structural support exists for a national M&E system. The focus is primarily on supporting CSOs, as demonstrated by the EU example. At the same time, involving local evaluators in conducting evaluations of international programmes strengthens individual M&E competencies.

Various educational programmes have been developed at all levels, including bachelor's and master's programmes at universities. However, the professional expertise in M&E practice is limited, and professional qualification and training quality varies. The introduction of an educational standard for M&E, a formal recognised certification system for M&E professionals, could be one possible step towards ensuring a high quality of evaluation practices. As an expert from civil society highlighted: "The M&E system should be supported by unified standards and methodologies at the national level, with clearly defined evaluation criteria, reporting requirements, and monitoring standards."

Although M&E professionals are available in Ukraine, limited awareness of the importance of M&E, combined with high demand from development partners, has resulted in a shortage of skilled M&E professionals. This has been further exacerbated by the war, with the relocation of skilled staff and a surge in international assistance (Antoniv et al., 2023).

The analysis conducted indicates that Ukraine's current training provisions are inadequately aligned with the country's evaluation needs. Although domestic M&E demand is low at the time of writing, international demand is high due to the increased international assistance and established M&E practices in humanitarian assistance and development co-operation. Ukraine's aspirations to align with EU standards and the important role of international aid in the country's recovery processes mean that the demand for qualified M&E professionals will likely rise.

4. CONCLUSION ON THE CASE STUDY: STRENGTHENING EVIDENCE-BASED DECISION MAKING IN UKRAINE

The final two chapters (4 and 5) of the discussion paper offer a reflection on the key findings. First, section 4.1 examines the main findings of the case study, focusing on the roles and capacities of different actors in the current national evaluation system in Ukraine. Second, section 4.2 outlines entry points, potential components and key actors for enhancing such a system in the future. Chapter 5 reflects on the implications of these findings for the broader discourse on developing evidence-based decision making in the context of armed conflict, fragility and crisis.

4.1 Summary Findings: The National Evaluation System and Capacities in Ukraine

Ukraine currently lacks a coherent national evaluation system for public policy making. The case study indicates that the evaluation culture in Ukraine is not well developed and that state actors' capacities for evidence-based decision making are insufficient. The status quo of the rudimentary national M&E structures and limited actual practice can be attributed to a lack of political will, resulting in fragmented regulatory frameworks and constrained institutional capacity among state actors. Furthermore, a predominantly accountability-focused approach undermines the potential of evidence-based learning. Figure 7 below outlines the main findings regarding the Ukrainian evaluation system, its actors and capacities. These findings are summarised and discussed in the following paragraphs.

Figure 7 Overview: National Evaluation System in Ukraine: Important Actors, Structures and Processes

Source: DEval, own illustration.

(1.) There is no unified legal framework or evaluation policy guiding M&E approaches at the national level.

Some sectors have seen a more robust establishment of M&E regulations than others, though there is great variance from sector to sector. Furthermore, these sectoral M&E regulations have not yet resulted in a well-established national evaluation practice of public policy. The lack of coherence within the Ukrainian legal doctrine has not yet been addressed. Government officials are not sufficiently aware of the importance of M&E, nor is there a political will to enhance M&E practices, leading to low prioritization of strengthening the evaluation framework and its actual implementation. Moreover, across all state actors, understanding of M&E is limited to oversight, with basic, primarily quantitative aspects of monitoring activities being applied. Policy monitoring in Ukraine focuses on keeping government spending accountable – emphasizing reporting, compliance, and control rather than investigating the success of policies and fostering a culture of learning from evaluations to improve impact of policies and practices. The absence of established M&E processes within the policy cycle, coupled with a lack of awareness, mean that the government rarely commissions independent evaluations. Consequently, the extent to which state actors (ministries and parliament) have established M&E structures and practices varies.

There is no co-ordinating body among state actors for evaluation in Ukraine. However, the study identified some bodies and actors with M&E responsibilities. In this regard, the Cabinet of Ministers (CMU) is of particular importance. Within the CMU, the Government Office for Coordination on European and Euro-Atlantic Integration, which reports to the Office of the Deputy Prime Minister for European and Euro-Atlantic Integration, currently monitors M&E practices – but this office's mandate is rather narrow and does not adequately address the increased needs that have arisen since Russia's full-scale invasion. It is clear that government bodies' capacities for evidence-based decision making are insufficient. To some extent, the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine (VRU) is also involved in M&E activities: as the legislative body, it has limited capacity to draft proper legislation and impact assessments, and its oversight mechanisms remain limited. Furthermore, the war has negatively affected parliamentary oversight and transparency mechanisms. However, the establishment of the Parliamentary Research Service in August 2022 represents a positive step towards strengthening the parliament's role in monitoring and using evidence in public policy making, as well as enhancing legislative processes.

M&E regulations vary in their advancement across policy sectors, resulting in a fragmented approach to M&E, with different legal provisions and initiatives for providing monitoring and oversight mechanisms, and limited reference to evaluation. Application of M&E standards and regulations varies across ministries: some have more developed M&E regulations, while others do not use M&E in their governance practices. State regional policy and digitalization are the most advanced fields in terms of M&E use. Despite M&E being used in some policy areas, it has not yet been institutionalised in Ukraine, nor have shared practices been established across the line ministries.

(2.) Non-state actors have already gained some capacities to conduct evaluations and use M&E within their organisations, but usage of evaluation results to hold the government accountable remains limited.

The country's legal framework fosters civil society participation in governance, with constitutional provisions guaranteeing the involvement of CSOs in decision making and monitoring processes. Although public consultations and councils do exist, their effectiveness is impeded by unclear legislation. CSOs are relevant actors in M&E, being beneficiaries and implementers of M&E capacity development programmes funded by international development partners. CSOs initiate their own M&E activities and are sometimes involved in external evaluations funded by development partners. Yet, their involvement in externally conducted national evaluations remains limited due to the scarcity of government-commissioned evaluations. CSOs generally demonstrate strong capacities for advocacy, having successfully influenced policy through advocacy projects and monitoring efforts. However, they notably lack a strategy for utilizing evaluation results to advocate for public policy reform.

Even before Russia's full-scale invasion, Ukraine's M&E structures and practices were rudimentary. The war has further deteriorated conditions for evidence-based public policy making and added additional challenges. Prior to the war, there was no established evaluation practice in Ukraine. The full-scale invasion exacerbated the need to address other urgent issues instead. Limited financial and human resources, the

prioritization of defence and security, and martial law have further restricted civil liberties and public consultation processes. Prior to the full-scale invasion, national data systems were relatively well developed to inform public policy and analysis, although they had some limitations regarding reliability and completeness. Against the backdrop of prioritizing and sequencing political measures in the reconstruction and recovery process, the formal introduction of statistical data utilization in the policy-making process in 2023 can be viewed as a positive step towards raising awareness of the importance of considering data in decision-making processes. However, the war has had a negative impact on the availability of information to the public, and data that informs strategic policy making, such as information on the implications of war, remains difficult to collect.

(3.) Several first steps towards developing a national M&E system were prompted by the EU accession process and the international recovery and reconstruction process. Since the full-scale invasion, the need for M&E in the public sector has increased, to facilitate recovery and reconstruction and to address rising M&E demands in the EU accession process framework. The Reforms Matrix consolidates various agreements and conditions with different international partners. Meanwhile, the EU accession process has led to new legislative initiatives, although implementation is at an early stage. The Deputy Prime Minister for Restoration of Ukraine and the Government Office for Coordination on European and Euro-Atlantic Integration were established, alongside other state institutions and co-ordinating bodies. These recently established structures and the number of actors indicate a high level of complexity regarding responsibilities and co-ordination efforts.

4.2 Conclusions: Entry Points for Strengthening Evidence-Based Decision Making in Ukraine

The development of an effective system that facilitates evidence-based decision making in Ukraine is a long-term process operating at various levels. The findings indicate that Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine has introduced further complexity and challenges to this undertaking. Although Ukraine has demonstrated high resilience, the ongoing war is straining the state's capacities. At the same time, the increased financial support from external development partners calls for a high degree of absorption capacity and transparency. The mapping exercise not only demonstrates the need for but also the feasibility of this approach, because it is facilitated by "windows of opportunities" and the existence of both external and internal drivers.

The subsequent section of this study contextualises the summary findings and concludes how national decision makers and international development partners can strengthen evidence-based decision making in Ukraine's public policy in the future.

Establishing a formalised, general evaluation policy or framework at national level may be particularly important for Ukraine. Globally, evaluations are rarely implemented at a national level but are more prevalent at secondary levels (Stockmann et al., 2020). However, this may be more useful for Ukraine due to its legalistic administrative culture, in which public institutions tend to operate in a top-down manner with a strong emphasis on adhering to established rules and formal procedures. In such an environment, legal codification can trigger and enable institutional change.

At the level of state actors, M&E capacities and awareness of the value of evidence orientation in public policy need to be strengthened, taking into account the important role of the government in establishing and fostering evidence-based decision making. Strengthening the competences and capacities of the CMU and subsequent bodies responsible for EU accession would be particularly useful. The findings suggest that the parliament's M&E capacities can be strengthened through the newly established research service units. Although the president does not currently play a leading role in M&E, the president's office could take on an agenda-setting role in advancing evaluation practices, similar to its leadership role in promoting the anti-corruption agenda. Politically, the will to establish evidence-based decision making – and awareness of its importance – remains low among high-ranked governmental actors and in parliament. If awareness of M&E's functions for evidence-based decision making were raised among these actors, they would have the agency to drive a co-ordinated, transparent process. Framing evaluation as a tool for (re-) establishing public trust in state institutions and enhancing the legitimacy of policy initiatives in the (post-) war context could generate

stronger political support, alongside the incentives provided in the framework of EU accession and recovery and reconstruction (see below). Furthermore, co-ordinating the reconstruction and recovery process, as well as the EU accession process, will require enhancement of M&E capacities and oversight mechanisms at governmental level.

A tangible step forward would be to evolve the currently dominant quantitative monitoring approaches into more comprehensive M&E practices integrated within governmental structures and processes. The existing M&E system merely tracks the completion of projects and programmes, with a focus on accountability and monitoring only. It lacks metrics to effectively assess the broader impact of recovery and reconstruction efforts. Tackling these issues would help ensure that project selection is grounded in comprehensive needs assessments of local communities, feeding into inclusive public policy making. Moreover, the considerable presence of international actors in individual projects that require co-ordination underscores the challenges associated with maintaining coherence and harmonization in the context of a substantial international recovery effort, in conjunction with the EU accession process.

To establish a learning-oriented evaluation system within public administration, Ukraine needs appropriate organisational structures that allow for institutional and organisational learning. It is essential to establish learning mechanisms within the public administration that will not be undermined by the high staff turnover in the Ukrainian civil service, which has been further exacerbated by the ongoing war. Furthermore, although short-term training programmes and individual skill-building initiatives funded by development partners deliver immediate outputs, such efforts risk becoming ineffective in the long term unless they are embedded within a broader framework of institutional learning. Individual capacity development can only become meaningful when there is a supportive legal and policy framework in place that individual civil servants can align with, given Ukraine's highly formalistic legal culture, where public administration is strongly rule-based and action takes place after being explicitly authorised by law. This means it is important to consider the tensions that may exist between the promotion of learning-oriented policy making, the strong, formalistic hierarchies and the focus on accountability. Although these tensions indicate that strengthening Ukraine's evaluation culture will be a long-term process, initiating structures, processes and practices may be considered a fundamental step.

The mapping of the Ukrainian evaluation system and capacities also identifies the potential for stronger involvement by non-state actors. Given their general expertise and knowledge in M&E and Ukraine's enabling environment for their activities, CSOs could play a more critical role in strengthening the national evaluation system, such as through oversight and advocacy, by using and calling for evidence as well as implementing evaluations and establishing standards and skills. This will help to improve the evaluation skills of individual evaluators and non-state actors. As the only Ukrainian Voluntary Organisation for Professional Evaluation (VOPE), the Ukrainian Evaluation Association (UEA) could play a leading role in this process. Uniting over 60 experts from diverse professional backgrounds, the UEA already contributes to the field by promoting ethical practices, connecting clients with qualified experts and informally co-ordinating efforts to address gaps in professional standards. It could serve as a valuable partner to government institutions seeking guidance on designing and implementing effective M&E systems, support awareness-raising, promote consistent practices across institutions, and help shape a more robust and effective evaluation culture.

War-specific challenges need to be addressed, while also considering the socio-economic and political conditions that predate the full-scale invasion and continue to affect evidence-informed decision making, including M&E structures and practices. In Ukraine's case, the underdevelopment of the M&E system is primarily the result of structural and political challenges relating to evidence-based decision making that existed before the war began. Although the war has added to the complexity by introducing unpredictability and volatility, an absence of robust evidence or data, limited access to information, and safety and security concerns, it is not the main reason for the absence of an evidence-based system. As illustrated above, the war's impact is reflected in various areas, such as limited capacities, shifted priorities and decreased transparency due to martial law.

Given the current rudimentary state of M&E practices at all levels and the lack of institutionalization of M&E in Ukraine, national M&E structures must crucially be incorporated from the outset of recovery and reconstruction efforts. Doing so would not only strengthen transparency and accountability but also ensure that external support is driven by data, continuous learning and adaptive management. In this context, the high international support provided to Ukraine can act as a key driver. Since external development partners play a decisive role in Ukraine, both the recovery and reconstruction process and the EU accession trajectory should prioritise transferring and institutionalizing evaluation capacities at the national level, while also considering lessons learnt from engagements in other crisis contexts and the associated risks. Ensuring national ownership of M&E structures and competencies will be critical to building a sustainable evaluation system that is grounded in the local context and supports evidence-based decision making and accountability. If not addressed adequately and early on, the system risks becoming overly complex, and the long-term effects of this could cause negative consequences. The latest EU progress report assesses Ukraine's capacities for evidence-based policy making as "insufficient" (EC, 2024a). Therefore, it is crucial to establish functional M&E structures at this current juncture, as reconstruction continues and the EU accession process progresses.

5. IMPLICATIONS FOR EVIDENCE-BASED DECISION MAKING IN FRAGILE AND CONFLICT-AFFECTED STATES

The world is facing growing challenges due to increasing geopolitical threats and the spread of disinformation and misinformation that risks undermining democratic institutions. Additionally, state fragility and armed conflicts remain ever more significant issues that continue to shape global stability. In Ukraine, Russia's full-scale invasion has prompted substantial international financial, technical and political support. Guided by the principle of "building back better", this support has fuelled Ukraine's broad recovery and reconstruction efforts while, simultaneously, Ukraine's EU accession process has been initiated to accelerate reforms, even amid ongoing war.

The study on Ukraine's national evaluation system and capacities, situated within the theoretical framework of lessons learnt from previous international engagements and EU accession processes, offers valuable insights for the international community and national stakeholders alike. These findings inform the enhancement of evidence systems in contexts marked by crisis, conflict and fragility. The following conclusions can be drawn based on the case study of Ukraine:

Strengthening evidence-based public policy making in fragile and conflict-affected states is a complex and multifaceted process. But this does not diminish its importance. Crisis, fragility and armed conflict pose a "stress test" for national governments and the international community alike. In highly complex, volatile and dynamic contexts with a massive inflow of international assistance, national governments must address the most urgent needs caused by fragility and crises, rebuild the country, and respond to reform requirements. This creates a policy paradox: precisely when evidence-based decision making is most critical, it also becomes particularly complex and challenging to implement. This finding holds true in both resource-scarce environments, where efficiency is paramount, and in resource-rich settings, where the focus shifts to maximizing impact while minimizing harm. As previous international efforts have shown, comprehensive support for state-building, peacebuilding, and development is accompanied by certain risks. The findings of this study suggest that Ukraine's present national evaluation system and capacities are not sufficient to guide comprehensive evidence-based recovery and reconstruction processes and EU accession. From looking at other countries' experiences, for example challenges related to focusing on impact, coherence and the avoidance of negative effects, it is clear that understanding and strengthening national capacities is essential.

M&E in fragile and conflict-affected states presents unique political and contextual challenges. Fragile and conflict-affected states are regularly characterised by limited evaluation capacity and underdeveloped and disrupted M&E systems (Better Evaluation Knowledge, 2024; Hassnain et al., 2021). In Ukraine's case, the identified challenges to evidence-based decision making are similar to those observed in other contexts

affected by armed conflict and fragility, such as political sensitivities or strong interests, unpredictability and lack of a robust evidence base, as well as safety and security concerns. Evidence-based decision making is often treated as a formal requirement rather than being genuinely integrated into the policy-making system. As outlined above, the war has imposed additional challenges to the low evidence orientation in decision making, although this was prevalent even before the full-scale invasion. Contextualization has demonstrated the resilience and functionality of the Ukrainian state in the face of Russia's aggression, while also identifying challenges, including those regarding public administration, transparency and rule of law.

To “build back better” during and after violent conflict, structures and processes need to be established to measure progress and improve harmonization, both among international partners and at the national level. Shared co-ordinating structures, supported nationally and internationally, are necessary for better co-ordination and alignment. If these structures are not set up efficiently, this could result in their duplication, putting additional pressure on the institutional capacities of the recipient country. Although co-ordinating mechanisms seem to be in place to harmonise the reconstruction and EU accession reform process efforts of development partners, Ukraine is having difficulties in aligning these processes at a national level and embedding them into the governance system. Furthermore, the complexity of the various processes and responsibilities is making it challenging to maintain oversight and navigate existing institutional frameworks, which could result in parallel processes being established.

Development partners hold leverage to incentivise evidence-based decision making. International development partners need to engage more explicitly with their role in promoting M&E practices. The case study of the national evaluation system in Ukraine reiterates the significant impact that the international community could have in promoting transparency and accountability standards. It illustrates how external development partners can incentivise or even demand stronger M&E practices while co-operating with a partner country. However, each development partner's level of leverage will depend on regional dimensions, quality of co-operation and credibility. In Ukraine, the prospect of EU membership has created an opportunity to reform and enhance M&E practices which must be realised. Although the country's EU accession process is still in its early stages, it is already clear that national M&E practices must be incorporated from the outset.

Do not wait for acute crises to end to start developing and strengthening evaluation systems. It takes time to understand and build effective systems that allow for evidence-based decision making on the scale required for comprehensive developmental and recovery processes. In countries affected by fragility and armed conflict, M&E systems are often not properly established even before an acute crisis, as discussed above. While an immediate crisis response may not allow for stringent evidence-based action from the outset, it is crucial to invest as early as possible in understanding and developing the affected country's systems and capacities for generating and making use of evidence. Should the enhancement of M&E systems be left unaddressed, the risks and challenges that have been identified will continue to exist, including negative unintended consequences from high levels of international assistance as well as limited ownership and alignment.

Resort to context-responsive approaches when supporting national evaluation systems and capacities. Designing an appropriate and context-sensitive approach to support the development of an evidence system requires a thorough understanding of existing systems and capacities, as well as internal and external drivers and incentives. The paper's findings reiterate the importance of a deep understanding of national evaluation systems within their specific political, social and historical contexts. A national evaluation system can be described in terms of specific structures and actors, including those who commission evaluations and utilise the results, as well as those who conduct the evaluations themselves (see section 3.2). Context-responsiveness means that the chosen approach may exhibit considerable variation: in Ukraine, for example, a legalistic, whole-of-government approach could enhance the effectiveness of evidence-based decision making at a systemic level. In other scenarios, a completely different approach may be deemed appropriate.

Specific measures in the domain of Evaluation Capacity Development (ECD) can encompass enhancing the capacities of individuals, organisations and societies as a whole regarding the commissioning, conducting and effective utilization of evaluations (DEval, 2025). ECD in fragile and conflict-affected states, similar to other external aid projects, requires a nuanced approach where the identification of needs, management of risks

and contextual entry points are all carefully considered to ensure a balanced and effective strategy. For example, systemic initiatives, such as strengthening governance and transparency through ECD, can yield significant benefits, but they may also unintentionally legitimise potentially problematic state actors. Similarly, collaborating with local evaluators can enhance their capabilities and improve evaluation quality – but it may also expose them to risks or inadvertently favour one group over another.

Learn lessons from other contexts but avoid generalizing. This paper's in-depth engagement with the case of Ukraine and M&E's role in this context highlights the importance of drawing lessons from other comparable settings. At the same time, the analysis of Ukraine's national evaluation system and its capacities underscores the need to balance the benefits of categorization and systematization with an appreciation for contextual specificity. The mapping exercise illustrates the analytical value of systematically considering concepts such as "fragility" and "armed conflict" when examining national evaluation systems. This discussion paper demonstrates that focusing on statehood and its deficiencies – in terms of authority, capacity and legitimacy – provides a valuable lens through which to understand the challenges and opportunities of evidence-based decision making at the national level. However, it is important to note that these categories can vary significantly, and the war against Ukraine exhibits distinct characteristics when compared with violent conflicts in other countries (see sections 2.1 and 3.1). In a context defined by protracted civil war and high levels of fragility across all dimensions of statehood, particularly without legitimate state actors to work with as international community, the conditions for strengthening evidence-based decision making may differ considerably from those in Ukraine. Nonetheless, the broader insights and conclusions presented in this paper remain relevant across a diverse range of contexts.

Understand the evaluation system, structures and actors first. To apply a context-sensitive approach, careful mapping of the country's evaluation system and capacities is crucial. Such mappings serve as critical tools for identifying systemic, organisational, and individual strengths and weaknesses, clarifying the roles and responsibilities of key stakeholders, and uncovering potential entry points for reform. The case study of Ukraine shows that, if adapted to the specific context, with consideration of research and ethical standards, profound assessments can be conducted even in adverse settings characterised by war (see Box 6). This approach could serve as a model to be used in other contexts with volatile developments.

Box 6 Mapping M&E Systems in Fragile and Conflict-Affected States: Reflection on the Process and Methodology

Mapping M&E systems in fragile and conflict-affected states requires a customised approach, as illustrated by insights from the analysis of Ukraine's national evaluation system and capacities (compare GEI, 2022). One key lesson is that effective and sound mapping is feasible when adapted to local conditions, emphasizing the importance of including diverse perspectives and listening to local expertise. A thorough grasp of national systems demands contextual knowledge and access to official documents, particularly given the complexity of institutional structures and processes. A volatile environment, where policy making may shift rapidly, further highlights the need for flexibility. In such contexts, mappings must strike a balance between specificity – by identifying concrete entry points for strengthening evidence-based decision making – and sufficient breadth to remain relevant amid institutional change, such as the government reshuffle in Ukraine in July 2025.

Data collection is frequently constrained, which requires pragmatic solutions such as combining remote and on-site methods (for example, prioritizing key expert interviews over broader participation), and using existing opportunities for data collection given the limited resources. In Ukraine, for instance, a summit bringing together CSOs was used for a targeted group discussion (see section 1.2). Lastly, although diverse stakeholder engagement in the mapping process can enhance awareness and strengthen national ownership, as reflected in the INCE methodology (INCE, 2025), such efforts may be hindered by limited capacity and political will, which must be considered in future applications. In this case, the focus was placed on initial mapping of the national evaluation system and identifying first entry points.

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7. ANNEX

7.1 Legislation Related to M&E of Public Policies: Examples

Among the government's and central executive bodies' documents that include specific references to M&E of policies and actions, the following are notable:

- Procedure for Functioning of the Unified Geo-Information System for Monitoring and Evaluating the Development of Regions and Territorial Communities (CMU, 2023d)
- "Methodology for Developing, Monitoring, and Evaluating the Effectiveness of Regional Development Strategies and Action Plans" (Ministry of Regional Development, Construction and Housing of Ukraine, 2016), which defines the composition, content and timelines for developing, monitoring and evaluating regional development strategies, including provisions for local executive authorities to establish monitoring groups to conduct monitoring and evaluate the effectiveness of regional strategies and action plans
- Law of Ukraine "On Culture" (VRU, 2010), which provides only a definition of M&E of the implementation of state policy in the field of culture, without detailing the approaches or principles for conducting these activities
- Order of the Ministry of Social Policy of Ukraine, Ministry of Economic Development and Trade of Ukraine, Ministry of Finance of Ukraine, State Statistics Service of Ukraine, and National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine "On Approval of the Methodology for Monitoring and Evaluating the Effectiveness of Social Support Programmes for the Population" (Ministry of Social Policy of Ukraine et al., 2017)
- Resolution of the CMU "On Approval of the Procedure for Monitoring the Provision and Assessment of the Quality of Social Services" (CMU, 2020b)
- Resolution of the CMU "On Approval of the Procedure for Monitoring and Evaluating the Degree of Accessibility of Physical Environment Objects and Services for Persons with Disabilities" (CMU, 2021b)
- Resolution of the VRU "On Establishing a Temporary Special Commission of the VRU on Monitoring and Evaluating the Effectiveness of the Activities of Local Self-Government Bodies and Local Executive Authorities in the city of Kyiv, the capital of Ukraine, during martial law" (VRU, 2024b)
- Resolution of the CMU "On the Implementation of an Experimental Project on Quarterly Monitoring and Evaluating the Effectiveness of Regional Governors, as well as the Heads of Kyiv and Sevastopol City State Administrations"

7.2 Key Platforms for Monitoring of War Damages and Reconstruction and Recovery Efforts

- **DREAM**³⁵ provides communities with the ability to submit their projects, showcase implementation stages and highlight results. It also enables development partners and Ukrainian authorities to monitor how funds are being spent.
- The **Register of Damaged and Destroyed Property**: information is entered into this register via reports submitted by both individuals and legal entities through the Diia portal. Legal entities can also submit reports through the Administrative Service Centres or notaries.
- The **"Recovery Spending Watchdog" project** has developed an independent monitoring system to track the spending of budgetary and international funds for recovery. It allows for analysis of and public engagement in monitoring reconstruction efforts. Information on the project is available on the **Big Recovery Portal**, which primarily relies on data from DREAM. While the public can use this platform to comment on and file complaints about specific objects (authorization required), the project also calculates risks associated with implementing recovery projects.

³⁵ The information was collected as part of implementing the project "Quality Analytics – Effective Recovery!" with the support of Isar Ednannia within the framework of the Ukraine Civil Society Community "Recovery" project, funded by the US Embassy in Ukraine.

- The **eRecovery service: Register of Compensation Requests** tracks how many owners of damaged or destroyed housing have received compensation. As of September 2023, 12,146 people have received compensation under the e-Recovery service, with over 41,000 applications submitted. However, detailed analytical information is not yet available.
- The project “**Providing Expert and Technical Support to the Government and Regional Administrations for Developing and Implementing Recovery Plans**” has developed several dashboards that provide information on basic community indicators, including: population size and dynamics, age composition, number of IDPs, people with disabilities, war veterans, number of educational institutions, capacity levels, primary healthcare infrastructure, housing infrastructure, and so on; residents’ needs in communities; results of surveys conducted among businesses and residents who have left their communities; and the status of urban planning documentation in communities, including the number of IDPs, the number of destroyed objects and so on. However, the project is limited by its one-time/irregular nature – collection of the survey data was completed in the first quarter of 2023, making it impossible to track changes happening in communities over time.
- **Analytical Platform for the Recovery of Cities and Communities in Ukraine**, an analytical tool developed by the Restart Ukraine team in collaboration with the UNDP Accelerator Labs. This is a two-tier online platform designed to assist with forming recovery plans for cities and communities while accounting for future risks and challenges. The platform is a GIS for collecting, analysing and visualizing geospatial data about territories. The GIS infrastructure is based on ArcGIS Online’s cloud technology.
- The **Kyiv Region Recovery Dashboard** is an interactive map that monitors expenditures for rebuilding damaged facilities in Kyiv Oblast. It provides information on reconstruction funding at district, territorial community and settlement levels, including the total number of objects, actual spending amounts, a list of companies receiving the largest reconstruction contracts and the primary reconstruction contractors.
- The **Kharkiv Recovery Dashboard** (Korzh, 2023) is an interactive map featuring objects that require investment and a system for monitoring the allocation of financial aid. This project was initiated and developed on a volunteer basis by the Kharkiv Regional Branch of EPAM Ukraine. At the time of writing, the platform has not yet been launched for public use. The damaged property registry could serve as a data source. The developers highlighted technical implementation issues in February 2024.

The Ministry for Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine is also developing a **GIS for Regional Development**, which will provide access to regional data in the form of layered interactive maps. These layers will include data on destruction, population changes, number of legal entities, access to social services, functional types of territories and more. Implementing this system will enable “smart” community development planning and evidence-based regional policy making. The GIS will consist of a public section, accessible to everyone, and an administrative section for verified data input, planning and monitoring. The latter will be available to communities, regional administrations, government organisations, and the State Agency for Restoration and Infrastructure Development of Ukraine. The GIS will also offer a unified framework for structuring planning documents, to automate the process of defining tasks and indicators for regional development. Furthermore, this system will interact with the Register of Damaged and Destroyed Property, the DREAM platform, and other government databases (Ministry for Communities, Territories and Infrastructure Development of Ukraine, 2024).

The **Recovery of Ukraine Analytics Catalogue** compiles research results, reports and policy briefs from leading analytical and research centres in Ukraine and worldwide on post-war recovery. It also features successful global case studies of rebuilding efforts after wars or natural disasters. The catalogue was created by the NGO Institute for Analytics and Advocacy, with financial support from the EU.

7.3 Capacity Development

Capacity Development in the Policy Analysis Field³⁶

The development of policy analysis capacity in Ukraine began in the mid-1990s, led by initiatives of the Institute of Public Administration under the CMU. This early phase was marked by significant international support, including technical and financial aid from various governments and organisations, which allowed policy analysis to be established as an academic and professional field in Ukraineⁱ. In 1995, this institution was transformed into the Ukrainian Academy of Public Administration (of the President of Ukraine). In 2003, it gained national status and changed its name to the National Academy of Public Administration under the President of Ukraine, then in 2021 it merged into Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv as the Educational and Scientific Institute of Public Administration and Civil Service. The National Academy for Public Administration played a critical role by incorporating policy analysis into its curriculum, offering specialised training and establishing relevant academic departments.

Since then, policy analysis and evaluation have become integral parts of the curricula at several institutions of higher education. Some examples include:

- Public policy and political process analysis at the department of history at Kamianets-Podilskyi Ivan Ohienko National University
- Policy Analysis Certificate Programme at the National University of “Kyiv Mohyla Academy”
- Public Policy Analysis at Educational and Scientific Institute of Public Administration and Civil Service of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv
- Methods of Policy Analysis, Public Policy Analysis and Evaluation, Data-Driven Policy Evaluation at Kyiv School of Economics

Importantly, in the latter course, a distinction is made between policy analysis and policy evaluation.

Training programmes and courses on this topic are also offered by several Ukrainian think tanks and CSOs. However, just as in the case of M&E, these programmes are rather sporadic. Examples of such programmes include:

- Lectures on policy analysis developed by a Ukrainian media non-profit organisation Internews Ukraine, with support from the International Renaissance Foundation – two of the nine lectures in the course deal with the role of M&E in policy analysis
- Instruments for policy analysis developed by the German Institut für Europäische Politik and the Ukrainian think tank Democratic Initiatives Foundation
- Training courses such as Evaluation of Public Policies and Programmes, Public Policy Analysis, and Implementation Mechanisms by the Institute for Policy Analysis and Strategies

Several online courses developed by different actors are available in Ukrainian. Examples of such programmes include the following:

- Public Policy Analysis, a course fully available subject to a simple e-mail registration, is available both via Kyiv Educational Hub and the VRU's e-learning portal. The course was developed by a group of business trainers under a project implemented by UNDP and funded by the EU.
- Fundamentals of Public Policy, a course available at the Ukrainian online education platform Prometheus, contains a chapter on “Forecasting effects of public policies” that discusses forecasting in policy analysis and development, as well as a chapter on policy M&E.

³⁶ The following information is based on Kiliyevych and Tertychka (2004).

Enhancing the M&E Capacity Development System in Ukraine³⁷

In Ukraine, the main challenges in M&E capacity development include:

- Lack of available and affordable training and professional development opportunities for evaluators. The UEA sometimes arranges lectures or brief workshops for its members, but those activities are not systematic and are conducted mostly by international experts on a pro bono basis.
- Lack of access to sources on M&E, such as international publications and books. Access to such resources is often fee-based, which means not everyone can afford it. Access to publications by international evaluation societies is granted to their members, but for some Ukrainian evaluators, especially early on in their careers, the membership fee may be prohibitive.
- Lack of an evaluation standard or certification programmes, which means that virtually anyone can enter the field of evaluation. The number of evaluations conducted in Ukraine is growing, and organisations that need to have their projects evaluated or international evaluation teams seeking a Ukrainian team member to support their evaluation may hire nationals with limited M&E experience and skills.
- Deficit of professional evaluators to conduct independent evaluations.

The UEA could be a logical “home” or driver and advocate for the system of training and professional development of Ukrainian evaluators and other M&E professionals. To address the multitude of demands for M&E specialists, a training system that works at different levels to provide opportunities to professionals at different stages of their careers is suggested:

- **Introductory:** understanding the role of M&E in projects and programmes, and covering the fundamentals of M&E, including basic data collection methods and report writing
- **Intermediate:** advanced evaluation designs, such as impact evaluation, theory of change and work with complex data
- **Advanced:** leadership roles in M&E, managing M&E systems and conducting large-scale evaluations

Such a system could also include some kind of certification, at least at the introductory level. Securing this certification would mean that an evaluator has formally verified their competency in fundamental M&E concepts and practices, such as collecting and analysing data, creating monitoring frameworks, and preparing basic evaluation reports. This verification would increase their professional credibility, providing formal proof of their qualifications and making them more attractive to potential employers or project implementers.

The introductory-level training could include the following topics (modules):

- Introduction to M&E: main concepts of results-based management, definitions, purpose, monitoring versus evaluation
- M&E legislative framework
- M&E in the project cycle: where M&E sits in the project cycle, why it is important
- Result chain, different levels of results (outputs, outcomes, impact), risks and assumptions
- Indicators and targets
- Data collection methods, sources of information, visualization
- Data management and utilization, report writing
- Gender-responsive M&E

This introductory-level course would be of interest not only for those who would like to pursue careers in M&E but also those who work for NGOs and are involved in grant writing or project management. The course

³⁷ The following information is based on Margolina (2024).

could be delivered online or offline. Depending on the delivery mode and availability of participants, it may be delivered as an intensive one- or two-week offline course or as a two-month online course for working professionals. A detailed curriculum could be developed by experienced UEA members, who can also deliver the training.

Courses at the intermediate or advanced level would be intended primarily for professionals interested in pursuing careers in M&E. While the introductory course should be taken in its entirety, courses at the higher levels could be taken independently of each other. Dividing the intermediary and advanced levels would be conditional: while the intermediate-level courses would focus on methods and approaches that can be used by an independent evaluator or look deeper into specific topics of the introductory course, the advanced level would focus on those managing complex evaluations and teams of evaluators. Therefore, the advanced level would include topics dealing with leadership and management in M&E.

An important difference between these two levels and the introductory course is that their development – and sometimes delivery – should involve international partnerships and experts. This approach would enable the curriculum to benefit from practical experience and expertise that may not yet be fully developed in Ukraine. International experts would bring experience and knowledge from working in diverse contexts to help design courses that are aligned with global best practices and the latest M&E advancements. Their participation in both the course development and delivery would also provide valuable insights, case studies and methodologies to enrich the learning experience for participants, ensuring they are equipped to apply M&E principles at a higher and more sophisticated level.

Sustainability of a Potential Training Programme

The sustainability of the training programme would depend on the two important factors: (1) its organisational home's ability to secure sufficient funding, and (2) the continuous demand for qualified M&E professionals across various sectors.

Regarding the institutional base, three options could be considered: an educational establishment (a university), a non-profit (the UEA or another CSO) or a commercial organisation/consulting firm. Of the three options, the university would be the most unrealistic for several reasons, including institutional rigidity and the slowness of most Ukrainian universities. The two other options, a non-profit or a consulting firm, each have their pros and cons, as discussed below.

At first glance, the UEA seems to be the most appropriate solution. It has an established presence and network in the Ukrainian and international M&E community, which may help in recruiting participants and experts. As a non-profit, it could potentially secure funding in the form of grants from development partners to cover operational costs. Finally, the UEA's reputation as an evaluation-focused organisation would lend credibility to the training programmes, potentially attracting more participants. However, the UEA is a small fee-based organisation – it does not have sufficient capacity to run such a large-scale programme without some kind of organisational capacity development, which would require structural changes and investments.

Planting the programme in a Ukrainian NGO other than the UEA could be another option. Ukraine has a vibrant civil society, with many strong NGOs able to implement complex long-term projects and programmes. Some of these NGOs provide capacity development activities for other NGOs, including various offline and online learning opportunities. Among the advantages of this option is, firstly, the flexibility of NGOs. They are able to find appropriate experts, organise tailored training programmes for various audiences and have experience in securing donor funding to sustain programmes. However, if the priorities of external actors change or if funding decreases, it could be difficult to sustain the programme in the long term. Moreover, unlike the UEA, an NGO that is not focused on evaluation may struggle to identify and recruit Ukrainian and international M&E experts, which could affect the quality of the programme, especially at the intermediate and advanced levels.

The third option would be to place the programme in a Ukrainian commercial entity or consulting firm. Such a model assumes that even if the programme is developed and initially piloted on a free-of-charge basis, it would then transfer to a fee-based delivery model. If successful, this would reduce reliance on external funding and ensure the programme can continue for as long as there is market demand. At the same time, this model could result in excessively high costs for participants, especially at the entry level. Demand for M&E training may fluctuate depending on the state of international funding and recovery efforts in Ukraine, making this model vulnerable to economic fluctuations.

Each of the three options discussed has its pros and cons. To build upon advantages and minimise gaps, a fourth option could be considered: a combination of the three options above. The UEA's participation would ensure the consortium's access to international evaluation associations and experts, while the presence of a strong NGO would add credibility when working with development partners and other NGOs. Moreover, by blending non-profit and commercial approaches, the programme could access both external funding (via non-profit partners) and fee-based revenue (via the commercial component), thus reducing reliance on any specific type of funding. However, this option also has its disadvantages, including the complexity of managing and co-ordinating different participants and balancing commercial and non-profit priorities.

Another way to ensure sustainability of the M&E training activities is to promote evaluation across various sectors. This approach would foster a culture of accountability, transparency and continuous improvement. It would strengthen decision making, ensure efficient resource use, and align organisations with both national and international standards. If the value of M&E were recognised across different sectors, this would result in increased demand for qualified M&E professionals, which would improve sustainability prospects for the training programme. By increasing demand for M&E professionals, securing stakeholder buy-in and fostering a culture of accountability, the programme could create a robust and self-sustaining ecosystem where evaluation practices are deeply embedded in Ukraine's development and governance sectors.

By involving international experts and institutions in developing curricula and delivering courses, Ukraine would benefit from global best practices, modern and innovative methodologies, and specialised knowledge that may not yet be fully developed locally. This approach would also elevate the credibility of the certification and training programmes.